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2 **Opportunities for Earth Observation to inform risk**
3 **management for ocean tipping points**
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14 **Abstract**

15 As climate change continues, the likelihood of passing critical thresholds or tipping points
16 increases (IPCC 2021). Hence there is a pressing need to advance the science for
17 detecting such thresholds. In this paper we assess the needs and opportunities for Earth
18 Observation (EO, here understood to refer to satellite observations) to inform society in
19 responding to the risks associated with ten potential large-scale ocean tipping elements:
20 Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation; Atlantic Subpolar Gyre; Beaufort Gyre; Arctic
21 halocline; Kuroshio Large Meander; deoxygenation; phytoplankton; zooplankton; higher
22 level ecosystems (including fisheries); and marine biodiversity. We review current scientific
23 understanding and identify specific EO and related modelling needs for each of these
24 tipping elements. We draw out some generic points that apply across several of the
25 elements. These common points include the importance of maintaining long-term,
26 consistent time series; the need to combine EO data consistently with *in situ* data types
27 (including subsurface), for example through data assimilation; and the need to reduce or
28 work with current mismatches in resolution (in both directions) between climate models and
29 EO datasets. Our analysis shows that developing EO, modelling and prediction systems
30 together, with understanding of the strengths and limitations of each, provides many
31 promising paths towards monitoring and early warning systems for tipping, and towards the
32 development of the next generation of climate models.

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35 **Keywords**

- 36 ● Earth Observation
- 37 ● Ocean Circulation
- 38 ● Ocean Deoxygenation
- 39 ● Ocean Ecosystems
- 40 ● Tipping Point

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43 **Article Highlights**

- 44 ● We review scientific understanding of ten potential tipping points in ocean
45 circulation, biogeochemistry, and ecosystems
- 46 ● We identify opportunities for Earth Observation to support improved models,
47 predictions and early warning of these tipping points
- 48 ● We identify how EO data can be combined with in situ data and models to maximise
49 the value of each

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90 All authors contributed to the writing and preparation of the manuscript.

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Competing Interests

94 There are no competing interests.

95 **1. Introduction**

96 The possibility of tipping behaviour in the ocean has a long history, heading back at least to
97 the pioneering work of Stommel (1961), who identified the potential for bistability and
98 threshold behaviour in an idealised two-box ocean circulation model that is controlled by
99 density differences arising from temperature and salinity variations. At the time, Stommel
100 did not have a specific application in mind, although he noted the important role of salinity in
101 the circulations of the Mediterranean and Red Seas. Only much later did oceanographers
102 realise the potential applicability of these ideas to global-scale flows such as the Atlantic
103 Meridional Overturning Circulation (AMOC), and hypothesise their role in major
104 palaeoclimatic variations (Rooth 1982, Broecker et al. 1985, Broecker 1987, see also
105 Stocker et al. 2024 (this issue)). In more recent times, the potential of tipping behaviour or
106 regime shift has been recognised in a much wider range of elements of the ocean-climate
107 system, including more regional circulation elements, elements of ocean biogeochemical
108 cycles, and ocean ecosystems (e.g. Swingedouw 2020).

109 While a number of definitions of ‘tipping elements’ (TEs) and ‘tipping points’ (TPs) have
110 been used in the literature, we consciously adopt a rather loose definition of a TE here as
111 an element of the Earth System whose response to a smoothly varying change in forcing
112 includes an abrupt, discontinuous or irreversible change when the forcing passes a certain
113 threshold (the TP). This definition brings together a number of responses that are similar at
114 the coarse level, but it will remain important when discussing each individual phenomenon
115 in depth to characterise the tipping behaviour more precisely. Some key questions for each
116 TE include: what is the relevant control parameter/forcing?; is there a critical threshold in
117 the forcing (bifurcation) or simply a nonlinear response to forcing?; if a threshold is crossed,
118 is there an element of irreversibility/hysteresis if the forcing is returned below the critical
119 value?; what is the timescale for adjustment to the new state if a threshold is crossed?; if
120 the forcing is reduced back to a subcritical value quickly enough, could tipping be avoided
121 (resilience time)?; could internal ‘noise’ or particularly rapid forcing changes make transition
122 to a new state more likely?

123 Many of the TPs discussed here can be considered examples of ‘high impact, low
124 likelihood’ (HILL) climate hazards. In many cases uncertainty in current scientific
125 understanding is so deep that it is not possible to provide robust estimates of how likely the
126 events are to occur. Such hazards pose particular risks to society because they may imply
127 changes that are greater than society’s planned capacity to adapt to climate change, in
128 some cases being even in the opposite direction to the expected changes. Adaptation
129 measures may be extremely costly or have undesirable side effects, and investing in such
130 measures when they probably will not be needed is not attractive. Despite these
131 uncertainties, it may be possible to develop tools that allow management of such HILL
132 risks, such as storylines of the impacts that would occur if the TP were crossed, and
133 observable early warning indicators (EWIs) that give advance notice that the TP is being
134 approached (Wood et al. 2023). The availability of reliable early warning of such events
135 would enable greater flexibility in responding to the risks, while avoiding the costs of
136 building resilience to an event that might never occur (see e.g. Marchau et al 2019). Earth
137 Observation (EO, taken here to refer to satellite observations) has the potential to provide
138 important elements of these tools, including direct monitoring of the TE itself, monitoring of
139 EWIs, and improved understanding of the processes and mechanisms at play in the TE,
140 that can be used to constrain and refine models.

141 To derive the full value from EO, it is frequently important to combine the EO data with *in*
142 *situ* observations and/or models. This can be done through: multivariate analysis of
143 observations (which typically requires some form of simple underlying process-based
144 model); assimilation of multiple observable types into more complex models such as
145 General Circulation Models (GCMs), to provide either a self-consistent estimate of past

146 variations (reanalysis), or an initial state to initialise forecasts/hindcasts of the ocean state;
147 or confrontation of free-running GCMs (no data assimilated) with the observations, in order
148 to evaluate the models themselves and point to paths for improvement. Assimilation of
149 multiple data types is challenging as the error and covariance characteristics of the different
150 variables need to be consistently specified. In this paper we aim to focus on EO variables,
151 while addressing the developments needed in modelling, data assimilation and in situ
152 datasets to deliver the full scientific potential.

153 This paper arises from discussion among a subset of the authors at the International Space
154 Science Institute (ISSI) Workshop on “Tipping Points and Understanding EO data needs for
155 a Tipping Element Model Intercomparison Project” in October 2022. We present a
156 perspective of ocean TPs, focusing on opportunities to exploit existing EO data or potential
157 new missions, to: monitor ocean tipping elements; provide useful early warning (EW) of
158 tipping; and evaluate and improve models. The paper builds on the previous study of
159 Swingedouw et al (2020), by considering more (ocean) TEs, and more potential EO
160 applications (not just early warning). We consider ten potential TEs (see below). The
161 selection of TEs reflects to some extent the expertise of the author team, but there is a
162 focus on TEs that are either intrinsically large-scale, or where more localised TEs are
163 expected to be relevant over a wide geographical range. We are nevertheless conscious
164 that some other potential ocean TEs or abrupt changes have been noted in the literature,
165 e.g. acidification and carbon cycle (Heinze et al. 2021, 2023), Mediterranean convection
166 sites (Schneider et al. 2014), North Sea circulation (Holt et al. 2018), occurrences of marine
167 heat waves (Benedetti-Cecchi 2021), tropical reefs (Lenton et al. 2019). We also do not
168 discuss here impacts thresholds in coastal systems such as mangroves, sea grasses and
169 coral reefs.

170 In Section 2, we consider six potential tipping elements of large (at least basin) scale ocean
171 circulation and biogeochemistry: Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation (Subsection
172 2.1); Atlantic Subpolar Gyre convection and circulation (2.2); Beaufort Gyre fresh water
173 storage (2.3); Arctic halocline (2.4); Kuroshio large meanders (2.5); and large scale
174 deoxygenation (2.6). Section 3 discusses four additional potential tipping elements in
175 pelagic ecosystems that are themselves more local/regional, but where processes may be
176 applicable to multiple geographical regions: phytoplankton (3.1); zooplankton (3.2); higher
177 trophic levels and fisheries (3.3) and overall biodiversity (3.4). For each of the ten tipping
178 elements considered, we provide a perspective on current knowledge of the nature of the
179 tipping element (processes, timescales, drivers and impacts of tipping), and needs and
180 opportunities for EO to advance knowledge of and resilience to the risks of tipping. In
181 Section 4 we synthesise the results of the previous sections, and suggest possible ways
182 forward for the use of EO data in this field.

183 **2. Tipping Points of Large Scale Ocean Circulation and** 184 **Biogeochemistry**

185 **2.1 Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation (AMOC)**

186 **2.1.1 Nature of Tipping Point**

187 The Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation (AMOC) is a global-scale system of currents
188 which transports warm water northwards in the Atlantic Basin. Much of the heat is lost to
189 the atmosphere in the North Atlantic high latitudes, and consequently the AMOC has a
190 fundamental role in shaping Northern Hemisphere climate (e.g. Bonnet et al. 2021). The
191 AMOC is often characterised as a global-scale ‘conveyor belt’ circulation (Broecker 1991),
192 driven by heat and fresh water exchanges with the atmosphere, and the consequent
193 density changes. While this view is undoubtedly a gross simplification, model studies
194 suggest that on decadal and longer timescales, coherent basin- or global-scale variations in
195 the circulation are possible. In this section we focus on large-scale variations whereas
196 North Atlantic subpolar gyre variability is discussed in Section 2.2.

197 The AMOC has been long recognized as one of the major tipping elements of the climate
198 system (Stommel 1961, Rooth 1982, Rahmstorf 1996, Lenton et al, 2008; Collins et al,
199 2013; Swingedouw 2020, Armstrong McKay et al. 2022; Boers et al 2022). AMOC
200 transitions (tipping) and multiple stable states have been found in a hierarchy of models,
201 ranging from simple box models through to comprehensive General Circulation Models
202 (GCMs). However not all climate models exhibit bistability (e.g. Schiller et al. 1997),
203 highlighting considerable variation among climate models which persists to the current
204 (CMIP6) generation (Jackson et al 2023). See Weijer et al. (2019) for a review.

205 Abrupt or gradual shifts in AMOC strength have been also identified in the paleoclimate
206 record. For example, AMOC bi-stability has been proposed as a mechanism for rapid
207 climate variability between glacial and interglacial periods in the Pleistocene (Dansgaard et
208 al. 1993; Blunier et al, 1998; Renssen et al. 2001, de Abreu et al. 2003, Lynch-Stieglitz
209 2017; Moffa-Sanchez et al. 2019), and during the last interglacial (Galaasen et al. 2014).
210 The Younger Dryas cold event has been associated with AMOC collapse following the
211 discharge of glacial lakes (Broecker et al 1985; 1987; Rooth 1982, Lehman and Keigwin
212 1992, O’ Hare et al 2011; Rind et al 2018). AMOC variations are also thought to drive the
213 “bipolar seesaw” leading to changes of opposite phase in the Arctic and Antarctic climates
214 (Broecker, 1998; Stocker, 1998; Rahmstorf, 2002; Stocker and Johnsen 2003, Skinner and
215 Elderfield, 2007; Pedro et al., 2011).

216 The wide range of model behaviour, and plausibility of abrupt AMOC changes, leads to a
217 pressing need for observations to constrain the models, and to provide independent
218 warning if such an event is approaching.

219

220 *Drivers of AMOC tipping*

221 The main mechanism that drives abrupt AMOC changes in models is the salt advection
222 feedback: if the overturning circulation carries relatively salty waters into the North Atlantic,
223 an AMOC slowdown would tend to make the Atlantic basin fresher, amplifying the
224 slowdown itself. Early comprehensive climate models were judged to have a ‘too-stable’
225 AMOC due to biases in the fresh water transport by the AMOC (e.g. Liu et al. 2017). These
226 biases are still present in more recent climate models, although advances in modelling and
227 resolution have reduced them to some extent (Deshayes et al. 2013, Mecking et al. 2016,
228 Hirschi et al 2020).

229 However overall AMOC stability depends on the combined effect of several positive and
230 negative feedbacks (e.g., Vellinga and Wood, 2002; Yin et al., 2006; Swingedouw et al.
231 2007; Hofmann and Rahmstorf, 2009, Hirschi et al. 2020). The AMOC only tips when the
232 destabilising effect of the salt advection feedback overcomes the stabilising feedbacks
233 (Jackson et al. 2017).

234 Key additional processes include the freshwater transport by the wind-driven gyre
235 circulation in the South Atlantic (Thomas and Fedorov, 2019) and North Atlantic (Wood et
236 al. 2019), discharges of excess freshwater through Fram or Davis straits, triggered by
237 changing winds (Haine et al 2015), cooling over the Atlantic Sub-polar Gyre (SPG) due to
238 storm track changes (Li et al, 2022), North Atlantic Oscillation (NAO) variability (Klus et al
239 2018), sea-ice interactions (Swingedouw et al. 2007), the strength of the ‘warming hole’
240 (Keil et al 2020), the rate of freshwater input (Wood et al 2019; Kim et al 2021) and other
241 atmosphere-ocean feedbacks which may be subdued, underestimated or biased in many
242 models (Gent 2018). Some such processes (e.g. fresh water input from the Greenland Ice
243 Sheet) are still only incompletely represented in current climate models (Swingedouw et al.
244 2007; Bakker et al. 2016).

245 The location and likelihood of tipping in climate models depends on model parameters that
246 are poorly known and need to be constrained using parametric uncertainty analysis.
247 Simpler models can help here, provided they can be shown to capture the key AMOC
248 tipping processes and feedbacks. Parameters can be estimated either by formulating the
249 simpler models in terms of observable quantities (Wood et al. 2019), or by Bayesian
250 ensemble inversion methods (e.g. Lux et al (2022), which showed that suitable paleo-proxy
251 timeseries may contain enough information to constrain the likely position of AMOC TPs).
252 By identifying the crucial parameters to constrain the position of TPs, it may be possible to
253 focus observational efforts to provide early warning. But these problems are still very much
254 at the research stage.

255 It is not clear whether there is a critical level of global warming that would trigger AMOC
256 collapse. Based on a literature survey, Armstrong McKay et al (2022) estimate a very broad
257 range of 1.4 to 8°C for such a threshold, if it exists. Other factors not strongly correlated
258 with warming level (e.g. response of the hydrological cycle to warming) may play a key role,
259 partly explaining the wide range of warming levels suggested by Armstrong McKay et al.
260 The results of Romanou et al (2023) suggest that even moderate climate forcing (such as
261 SSP2-4.5) may be sufficient to drive the AMOC over a threshold.

262 Noise induced transitions, in which internal climate variability causes a temporary AMOC
263 collapse, have recently been shown to be possible in future climate simulations (Castellana
264 and Dijkstra 2020). Romanou et al. (2023) in a fully coupled climate model and without
265 applying external freshwater forcing, found evidence of such noise-induced transitions in a
266 state-of-the-art climate model (NASA-GISS-E2-1-G), spontaneously arising from stochastic
267 variability of high latitude freshwater fluxes into the ocean and with an AMOC off state
268 lasting for about 800 years. Observational requirements to initialise prediction of such
269 behaviour are not currently known.

270 Rate induced tipping (Stocker and Schmittner 1997, Alkhuon et al. 2019, Ritchie et al
271 2022) might also occur: too-fast forcing variations (e.g. greenhouse gases or fresh water
272 input) may cause the AMOC to tip, even before the forcing reaches a critical level. This
273 implies that safe climate mitigation pathways need to consider rates of change as well as
274 the final destination. Further, given that future mitigation strategies may eventually lead to
275 drastic reductions to GHGs, more understanding is needed of potential abrupt changes
276 under ‘overshoot’ or negative emissions scenarios (e.g. Schwinger et al 2022).

277

278 *Timescales of tipping*

279 Based on a literature survey, Armstrong McKay et al (2022) suggest a timescale for AMOC
280 collapse, once a threshold is passed, of 15-300 years, consistent with timescales estimated
281 from a range of model studies (Bryan 1986, Jackson and Wood 2017, Weijer et al. 2019,
282 Sinet et al. 2022).

283 As discussed earlier, models might be too stable (Liu et al. 2017), and the processes that
284 spread the freshwater discharge from GIS might be too slow (Swingedouw et al. 2022),
285 hence the timescales from CMIP6 (Coupled Model Intercomparison Project, Phase 6)
286 models are possibly too long. Shorter timescales were inferred from the paleoclimate
287 record; for example the termination of the Younger Dryas cold event took only 10 years
288 (Alley and Agustdottir 2005). The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change's (IPCC's)
289 6th Assessment Report (IPCC, 2021, referred to as AR6) concludes that the AMOC will not
290 collapse within this century, but only assigns 'medium confidence' to that conclusion,
291 highlighting the poor capabilities of present-day models to represent a number of crucial
292 processes.

293

294 *Impacts of tipping*

295 A shut-down of the AMOC would have global impacts on climate. As well as the well-known
296 impacts over the Euro-Atlantic sector (e.g. Jackson et al. 2015, Bellomo et al. 2023), it
297 would lead to more extensive Arctic ice and warming of the Southern Hemisphere. The
298 Inter-tropical Convergence Zone (ITCZ) would be expected to migrate southward and the
299 global water cycle perturbed with weaker Indian and Asian summer monsoons (Buckley
300 and Marshall 2016, Wassenburg et al 2021). El Nino-Southern Oscillation (ENSO)
301 variability may be reduced (Orihuela-Pinto 2022) and shifted eastwards (Williamson et al
302 2018). Sea levels would rise on the western side of the North Atlantic and Atlantic storm
303 tracks shift northward and become more intense (IPCC 2019).

304 These effects would be expected to lead to a decrease in marine productivity in the North
305 Atlantic, a reduction in Sahelian, South Asian and part of Amazonian rainfall, and a
306 decrease in the number of tropical cyclones in the Atlantic (IPCC 2019). While detailed
307 sectoral impact studies are few (e.g. Ritchie et al. 2020), the societal impacts would be
308 expected to be far-reaching (e.g. DeFrance et al. 2017).

309

310 *AMOC Early Warning signals and proxies*

311 As discussed in Swingedouw et al 2020, to monitor AMOC shifts and identify possible TPs
312 we need adequately long records, e.g. of temperature and salinity in the North Atlantic and
313 transports across various latitudes (as in Frajka-Williams et al. 2019). However that may
314 still not be sufficient to obtain early warning signals (EWS). Since direct AMOC
315 observations have only become available fairly recently, it is likely that practical early
316 warning signals will need to use various proxies or fingerprints of the AMOC to obtain long
317 enough samples.

318 Low order dynamical system theory suggests that near a bifurcation point systems become
319 more sluggish in response to small perturbations (Held and Kleinen 2004; Carpenter and
320 Brock 2006; Boulton et al 2014) i.e. increasing autocorrelation and variance. A few studies
321 have highlighted that recent changes in various AMOC proxies/fingerprints, might be
322 exhibiting such a change in autocorrelation properties (Boers 2021, Michel et al. 2022),
323 highlighting the potential approach of the AMOC to a tipping point. Because a long enough
324 historical time series of the AMOC is not available, these studies unavoidably depend on
325 proxies or 'fingerprints', i.e. spatio-temporal observations of other variables that are

326 correlated with AMOC changes, e.g. SST (Dima and Lohmann (2010), Rahmstorf et al.
327 (2015), and Caesar et al. (2018)), subsurface hydrography (Chen and Tung 2018, Fraser
328 and Cunningham 2021), EO gravity data (Landerer et al. 2015), and surface altimetry in
329 combination with various *in situ* observations (Willis 2010, Frajka-Williams 2015, Mercier et
330 al. 2015). Both the consistency of the proxies (e.g. Little et al. 2020, Kilbourne et al., 2022)
331 and their relevance for AMOC tipping as opposed to recent variability (Jackson and Wood,
332 2020) remain the subject of debate. Meanwhile more process-based early warning
333 indicators (e.g Alkhayoun et al. 2019) are at an early stage of research.

334

335 **2.1.2 EO needs and opportunities:**

336 EO can play a valuable role in monitoring the AMOC and providing insights into key
337 processes. However, at least on the 5-10 year time horizon, it will be essential to use EO
338 alongside key *in situ* datasets, (trans-basin arrays, Argo, Arctic Ocean exchanges), which
339 observe sub-surface signatures of the AMOC that are inaccessible to satellite instruments.

340 Long-term consistency and continuity of existing datasets is particularly critical because the
341 (at least) decadal timescale of AMOC tipping means that early warning indicators could be
342 contaminated by data inhomogeneities.

343

344 *Proxies*

345 Proxy indicators ('fingerprints') of the AMOC give the opportunity to monitor in future at
346 locations where trans-basin sections are not available or practical, and potentially allow
347 longer past timeseries to be constructed, opening up greater options for early warning.
348 SST, SSH and gravity observations have been identified as particular opportunities for EO.
349 However there is substantial disagreement between different proxy timeseries, while
350 modelling (Jackson and Wood 2020) suggests that no single proxy can capture all aspects
351 of AMOC variability (natural variations, response to global warming, tipping).

- 352 • Work is therefore needed to develop *robust, multi-variate* AMOC proxies, probably
353 combining EO and *in situ* data, for monitoring and attribution of future AMOC
354 change.
- 355 • Machine learning, trained on a range of model data, potentially provides novel
356 opportunities to develop such multivariate proxies (e.g. DelSole and Nedza 2022,
357 Solodoch et al. 2023, Michel et al. 2023).

358

359 *Processes*

360 Improved estimates of heat and fresh water exchanges with the subpolar basin will allow
361 improved monitoring of the drivers of AMOC change and hence potential early warning of
362 major changes. This includes surface heat and freshwater fluxes, water inputs from rivers
363 and the Greenland ice sheet, and Arctic exchanges

- 364 • Key regions for monitoring include freshwater and ice transports across
365 Fram/Denmark and Davis Straits as well as storage of freshwater in the different
366 subpolar basins (Haine et al 2015) and ice edge/melting rates, in order to estimate
367 changes in freshwater budgets of the deep water formation sites (Lobelle et al
368 2022).The potential for EO to inform ice transports in particular is discussed in
369 Section 2.3.2.
- 370 • Polar regions, western boundary currents, storm tracks, and the subtropical-
371 subpolar transition zone in the North Atlantic (Buckley and Marshall 2016 and
372 references therein) are key regions for surface heat and freshwater exchanges.
373 Advances may best be delivered through intensive, localised multi-platform

374 campaigns, combining EO with *in situ* observations and high resolution models to
375 evaluate climate models and develop improved parametrisations..
376 ● Improved observational resolution of estuaries and coastal regions is needed, to
377 better define their role in basin scale heat and regional freshwater budgets
378

379 *Modelling*

380 A range of model experimentation is needed to inform future monitoring systems. Much of
381 this could potentially be done as part of the emerging TipMIP programme (Tipping Point
382 Model Intercomparison Project, <https://tipmip.pik-potsdam.de/>), building on recent
383 experiments in the North Atlantic Hosing Model Intercomparison Project NAHosMIP
384 (Jackson et al 2023). Modelling developments include:

- 385 ● Generating plausible scenarios (storylines) of AMOC tipping, moving from traditional
386 'hosing' experiments to a more direct link with greenhouse gas forcing. This should
387 include scenarios of bifurcation-induced, noise-induced and rate-induced tipping.
388 These scenarios can be used to identify mechanisms of tipping and to develop
389 physically-based early warning indicators.
- 390 ● Understanding why different climate models have different AMOC tipping behaviour,
391 and identifying circumstances in which the AMOC is likely to tip (either properties of
392 the model climate system, or particular emissions pathways likely to result in
393 tipping). This can inform missions to target key areas of process uncertainty.

394

395 *Data assimilation, reanalysis and prediction*

396 Assimilation of multiple data types into advanced models (reanalysis) provides a synthesis
397 of observations, which are themselves sparse and incomplete, with physical process
398 understanding. Current reanalysis products capture many aspects of AMOC variability seen
399 at the three trans-basin *in situ* AMOC sections (Figure 1), and allow the observations from
400 the sections to be extended back in time, providing a longer historical context (Figure 1d).
401 However, current reanalyses by no means capture all features seen in the sections.
402 Comparison with the SAMBA (South Atlantic MOC Basin-wide Array) section (Figure 1c) is
403 quite poor; however Baker et al. (2023) show that the reanalysis is well correlated with an
404 alternative estimate of monthly-mean AMOC variability on this section, derived from
405 combined altimeter SSH and *in-situ* hydrographic data (Dong et al. 2023).

406 Future development may consider the following:

- 407 ● Assimilation of new data types, e.g. surface salinity measurements provided by
408 SMAP (Soil Moisture Active Passive) and SMOS (Soil Moisture and Ocean Salinity)
409 (Vinogradova et al 2019, Boutin et al. 2023), perhaps also with higher spatial
410 resolution, and improved coverage at high latitudes (Estella-Perez et al. 2020)
- 411 ● Improved data assimilation methods (e.g. Polkova et al. 2019, Barthélémy et al.
412 2023), simulators and Observing System Simulation Experiments are needed to
413 make the most of the information in existing EO datasets and guide future missions,
414 e.g. most current data assimilation systems give low or zero weight to altimeter data
415 outside the subtropics, due to the challenge of consistently combining multiple data
416 types, especially in the subpolar region where stratification is weak but dynamically
417 important.
- 418 ● While AMOC tipping is likely to take longer than decadal timescales, decadal
419 prediction systems, initialised with a wide range of observations, may give early
420 indications of whether observed changes show the beginning of a longer term trend
421 or simply represent random variability.

422

423

424 **Figure 1.** Reconstructions of AMOC from two global ocean reanalysis products: GloSea5
 425 (Jackson et al. 2016, 2019) and GloRanV14 (Baker et al. 2022, 2023), compared with direct
 426 estimates on three in-situ sections: (a) OSNAP in the subpolar gyre (Fu et al. 2023), (b) RAPID-
 427 MOCHA around 26.5°N (Moat et al. 2023) and (c) SAMBA around 34.5°S (Kersalé et al 2020,
 428 2021). In each case the period shown is that for which direct observations are available. In (c)
 429 only the GloRanV14 product is shown, as issues with the altimeter assimilation in the earlier
 430 GloSea5 product caused spurious MOC features at this latitude. In (d) is shown the 12-month
 431 running mean AMOC at RAPID-MOCHA, back to the start of the reanalysis (1993, coinciding
 432 with the start of precision altimetry), illustrating the potential of reanalysis to provide a longer
 433 historical perspective on limited in-situ timeseries.

434

435

436 2.2 Atlantic subpolar Gyre

437 2.2.1 Nature of tipping point

438 Convection in the Labrador and Irminger seas south of Greenland and the associated
 439 Subpolar Gyre (SPG) circulation form a regional ocean circulation element, that is related to
 440 the larger scale AMOC, but is not the same thing, as a substantial component of the SPG
 441 circulations recirculate regionally without a direct impact on the global circulation. The SPG
 442 circulation has been proposed as a climate tipping element with medium confidence by
 443 Armstrong McKay et al. (2022). That study was based on analyses of CMIP5 (Sgubin et al.
 444 2017) and CMIP6 (Swingedouw et al. 2021) databases and the IPCC Special Report on
 445 Oceans, Cryosphere and Climate Change (SROCCC, Collins et al. 2019). Armstrong McKay
 446 et al. (2022) estimated with high confidence that the SPG might have a global warming
 447 threshold of $\sim 1.8^{\circ}\text{C}$ ($1.1\text{-}3.8^{\circ}\text{C}$) and a tipping timescale of ~ 10 years (5-50 years). The impact
 448 of such a collapse of the SPG might be substantial for the climate in the bordering regions
 449 (Collins et al. 2019, Oltmanns et al. 2020, Sgubin et al. 2019) but also with wider large-scale
 450 teleconnections in the tropical areas, as well as for marine biogeochemistry (e.g. Gary et al.
 451 2020). The Little Ice Age has been linked to weakening of the SPG (Michel et al. 2022)

452 possibly due to large exports of sea ice that followed atmospheric blocking relaxation
453 (Lapointe and Bradley 2021).

454 Nevertheless, we argue here that there is large uncertainty concerning the risk of this
455 system to tip, given the high dependency of the collapse of the SPG on the model
456 considered. Generally speaking, there are fewer models that do show a rapid collapse of
457 the SPG than ones showing none or very gradual ones. Also, the Arctic and North Atlantic
458 basins exhibit a high degree of variability and complexity, implying interactions between the
459 ocean, the atmosphere and the cryosphere as well as fine-scale processes (Yashayev et al.
460 2015, Yashayev and Loder 2016; Romanou et al 2023), which even further decrease the
461 confidence we might have in the current generation of climate models. The models showing
462 a tipping are among the best in terms of ocean stratification both in CMIP5 and CMIP6.
463 Stratification is indeed a key variable of ocean dynamics, in particular for what concerns
464 convection, a central element of the SPG. It is at the heart of the positive salt advection
465 feedback arising from this system: if convection ceases in the Labrador and Irminger Seas,
466 the North Atlantic drift is no longer steered into these basins, and the supply of tropical salty
467 waters in these seas is reduced, leading to a strong halocline that further suppresses
468 convection.

469 This positive feedback can lead to a very stable new steady state with the risk of
470 irreversibility and hysteresis behaviour (Born et al. 2013), which has nonetheless been
471 poorly evaluated in the literature up to now. The threshold of convection is related to
472 surface density, mainly driven by Sea Surface Salinity SSS (Swingedouw et al. 2020;
473 Romanou et al, 2023). For a given critical SSS threshold, the temperature cooling in winter
474 is not sufficient to destabilize the water column: the freezing point is reached before
475 convection can occur (as e.g. in the Arctic), so that sea ice is forming in place of
476 convection. As shown in Swingedouw et al. (2020), in CMIP5 models, the threshold might
477 be relatively close to the present-day observed state.

478 A strong freshwater anomaly is building in the Beaufort gyre from the Arctic, so that there is
479 now considerable risk that this freshwater might flush in the SPG (Zhang et al. 2021, Lin et
480 al. 2023, see Section 2.3). Given that the SPG system already recently experienced its largest
481 freshening for the last 120 years in its eastern side (Holliday et al. 2020), this is raising serious
482 concerns.

483 **2.2.2 EO needs and opportunities**

484 *Early warning*

485 The potential proximity to a threshold in SSS in the SPG highlights the need to use models
486 initialized towards observations to include the recent freshening of the North Atlantic - Arctic
487 sector. Such models starting from observed initial conditions constitute the decadal climate
488 prediction systems. More than 10 such systems are developed around the world (WCRP
489 decadal prediction) and provide predictions every year for the next decade (Polkova et al.
490 2023). Those models are assimilating the most recent EO (typically SST and altimetry)
491 alongside in situ data such as Argo, and are therefore making a good integration of those
492 data into a potentially useful early warning system, but should also integrate new SSS
493 products in their assimilation scheme. The increase in error of SSS products with increasing
494 latitudes is a limitation for data assimilation, which we hope might be improved in the near
495 future. Particular opportunities include:

- 496 ● Refinement of some components of the radiative transfer modeling used in the salinity
497 retrieval chain, such as the dielectric constant or sea surface roughness modeling
498 (e.g. Boutin et al. 2023)
- 499 ● Application of new Radio Frequency Interference (RFI) mitigation techniques (e.g.
500 Bonjean et al. 2024), planned to be applied in the future version of CCI v5 SSS.

- 501 • Develop corrections for contamination by the proximity of sea ice (Jiménez et al 2021)

502 In the longer term, the Copernicus Imaging Microwave Radiometer (CIMR), scheduled for
503 launch in 2028, should achieve better radiometric resolution and stability, powerful filtering of
504 RFI-contaminated measurements, and provide multi-frequency measurements that should
505 enable improved corrections of temperature- and wind-related effects.

506 The use of lower frequencies than L-Band that are more sensitive to SSS in cold waters is
507 another potential way for reducing SSS errors in cold waters (Johnson et al. 2021). The
508 CRYORAD mission idea, recently selected by the European Space Agency ESA, is
509 proposing such a concept. Nevertheless, the decadal prediction systems usually exhibit very
510 large drift when starting from an observed state (Bilbao et al. 2021). This is due to the model
511 biases and the fact that, starting from an observed state, the model usually drifts towards its
512 own mean state. In the SPG, this can be crucial, since CMIP6 climate models usually exhibit
513 a strong cool bias, so that the drift is usually a cooling drift, which might prevent the possibility
514 of predicting a strong cooling that might really occur. The value of bias correcting the
515 forecasts to remove drift, in a case where a tipping point is about to be crossed, is therefore
516 limited. Improvements concerning the initial shock of a decadal prediction system is therefore
517 strongly needed in order to provide skillful prediction of the SPG fate (Polkova et al., in
518 press.). Such improvements might be achieved through reduction of model bias, through
519 assimilation of new data types such as SSS, or through improved methods of assimilating
520 multiple data types into biased models, especially at depth (e.g. Polkova et al. 2019; see also
521 altimetry at high latitudes, see Section 2.1)

522 The direct use of EO observations as independent early warning systems might be very
523 relevant for the SPG. In this respect, existing systems that monitor SSS (e.g. SMAP and
524 SMOS, Vinogradova et al. 2019, Boutin et al. 2023) may provide important ground-truth
525 information. The recent SSS data from EO observations (CCI) are shown in Fig. 2 as
526 compared to *in situ* ones from EN4 and ISAS. The different SSS products are mainly
527 consistent, they do not entirely agree with each other for the recent trends in terms of their
528 best guess. While EN4 and ISAS show a relatively stable SSS evolution in the 2010s, the
529 CCI product exhibits a large increase, mainly due to an upward shift in the years around 2013.
530 This upward shift is reduced with the most recent CCI version which was better filtered for
531 radio frequency interferences even though inconsistencies remain. Understanding and
532 resolving this type of inconsistencies between the observation products might be required to
533 better assess the crossing of a SSS tipping point in the SPG system, which remains also to
534 be better estimated in climate models.

535 Another avenue of research might be to better analyse models showing abrupt changes in
536 their SPG and the way their patterns in some observable variables evolve just before the
537 collapse. This approach, which can be seen as a space-for-time substitution (Dakos et al.
538 2010) has been used for the Amazon rainforest (Verbesselt et al. 2016) and might be very
539 promising for the ocean realm. In this respect the SSH, SST and SSS observations might be
540 very relevant and useful, notably given their already relatively high resolution in space (~25
541 km) as compared to CMIP6 models (gridpoints usually larger than 50 km). Observations of
542 the Arctic, in terms of SSS and sea ice cover and transport might be also informative, given
543 the risk of a massive flush of freshwater from the Arctic towards the SPG. In this respect,
544 reduction in the errors of SSS at such very high latitudes (Estella-Perez et al. 2020) should
545 be considered as a key requirement for future EO products.

546 *Model development and evaluation*

547 Present-day climate models are missing key processes of the SPG dynamics (Le Corre et al.
548 2020). In particular, CMIP6 models poorly represent the role of eddies, notably for the spread
549 of freshwater anomalies from Greenland Ice Sheet (GIS) melting (Martin and Biastoch 2023,

550 Swingedouw et al. 2022), but more generally concerning water transformation (Lozier et al.
 551 2019), a key process for stratification properties of the SPG (Desbruyeres et al. 2019, Hirschi
 552 et al. 2020). In this respect, next generation models should try to better represent fine scale
 553 processes, either through improved parametrization or grid-zooming in some key locations
 554 (Hewitt et al. 2020, Zanna and Bolton 2020). The challenge in modelling is compounded by
 555 the fact that seasonal sea ice cover in the SPG area plays a crucial role in modifying
 556 atmosphere-ocean buoyancy fluxes. Improved resolution of EO products will be decisive in
 557 this respect to better assess the dynamics of those processes, and can be used also for
 558 spatial early warning, or to evaluate freshening on and off the Greenland coast (e.g. Castelao
 559 et al. 2023), relative to EO-based estimates of meltwater from the ice sheet (e.g. Bamber et
 560 al. 2019). Finally, consistent assimilation of multiple EO and *in situ* data types into models is
 561 a major challenge, especially in regions such as the SPG where stratification is weak.
 562 Improvements in this area have the potential to extract greater value from the available
 563 datasets for modelling and prediction systems.

564

565

566 **Figure 2.** SSS time series since 1950 averaged the subpolar gyre defined as the box 60-0°W,
 567 45-65°N for different monitoring systems. In black is represented the EN4 product and in green
 568 the ISAS products, both of which are mainly based on *in situ* observation records, notably from
 569 ARGO from 2004. In blue and red are recent products from CCI in two different versions (Boutin
 570 et al. 2021a,b). The overlap represents an upper estimate of the error for each product. It is
 571 estimated as the annual and spatial mean of the uncertainty provided at the gridpoint level. The
 572 mask from CCI v4 products using only gridpoints without sea ice has been applied to all products
 573 to allow a correct comparison of the data products.

574

575 **2.3 Beaufort Gyre freshwater accumulation and release**

576 **2.3.1 Nature of tipping point**

577 The circulation of the upper Arctic Ocean can be schematically characterized by two main
578 features, i.e., the Beaufort Gyre (BG) and the Transpolar Drift (TPD) (Timmermans and
579 Marshall 2020). They represent the sea ice and upper ocean response to the large-scale
580 atmospheric forcing in the Arctic – North Atlantic region dominated by the Beaufort high
581 (BH), accompanied by anticyclonic winds, and the Icelandic low (IL), accompanied by
582 cyclonic winds. The latter represents a large persistent atmospheric low-pressure centre
583 located between Iceland and southern Greenland and it is the main atmospheric driver of
584 the North Atlantic Subpolar Gyre (SPG) discussed in section 2.2. Notably, the North Atlantic
585 storm track originating from the IL has a strong effect on winter weather over Europe and
586 North America (Serreze and Barry 2005) and its northerly shift represents the positive
587 phase of the North Atlantic Oscillation (NAO), which can affect the BG (Moore et al. 2018),
588 hence the BG.

589 The BG anticyclonic circulation tends to trap both sea ice and relatively fresh water within,
590 which sets the vertical stratification in the western Arctic (Timmermans and Toole 2023).
591 The sea ice present in the BG for most of the year is not only a source of freshwater in
592 summer but also modulates the wind momentum transfer, which drives the gyre. Its thinning
593 and decline over the past decades (Ding et al. 2017) increase the solar radiation and wind
594 momentum (Rampal et al. 2009) transfer to the upper ocean, hence the intensification of
595 the BG, an increased accumulation of freshwater within (Figure 3), and a stronger cold
596 halocline (CH, see section 2.4 for more discussion). Estimates of freshwater content in the
597 BG show significant interannual variability superimposed over the overall increasing trend
598 (Proshutinsky et al. 2019). The BG freshwater content over the seasonal cycle varies by
599 approximately $4\text{-}5 \times 10^3 \text{ km}^3$ between maximum in December and minimum in April
600 (Proshutinsky et al. 2009), while it has increased by approximately $6.4 \times 10^3 \text{ km}^3$ from 2003
601 to 2018, which represents a 40% increase relative to the climatology of the 1970s
602 (Proshutinsky et al. 2019).

603 Any significant release of freshwater from this reservoir into the North Atlantic could impact
604 the wintertime deep-water formation and stability of AMOC and SPG, as discussed in
605 sections 2.1-2.2. Export of such “Great Salinity Anomalies” (GSAs) out of the Arctic and its
606 propagation in the subpolar North Atlantic has been observed in the past (Dickson et al.
607 1988; Belkin 2004), including more recently (Bilo et al. 2022). While the consequent positive
608 buoyancy flux at the surface of the subpolar Atlantic has been shown to freshen subpolar
609 waters produced by deep convection, or to suppress deep convection all together (Dickson
610 et al. 1988; Bilo et al. 2022), its impact on the circulation of the SPG has been less clear.
611 Comparison of the advection rate of the observed GSA events in the 1970s, 1980s, and
612 1990s, reveals a substantial intensification of the circulation in the SPG (Belkin 2004).

613 Recent analysis by Lin et al. (2023) of an extensive hydrographic dataset from 2003 to
614 2019 and satellite-derived dynamic ocean topography data shows that the BG has
615 transitioned to a quasi-stable state over the past decade, as represented by the sea surface
616 height and freshwater content. They also find that the center of BG has shifted
617 southeastward (also see Figure 3) due to regional wind forcing, and the CH layer within the
618 BG has thinned significantly. The southeastward movement of the BG moves its freshwater
619 closer to the Arctic gateways to the subpolar Atlantic (Canadian Arctic Archipelago and
620 Fram Strait). If continued, such changes could change the current stable state of the BG
621 and allow a release of freshwater into the Atlantic.

622 **2.3.2 EO needs and opportunities**

623 The primary hydrographic data on the evolution of the BG and its freshwater content have
 624 been provided by *in-situ* measurements as part of the Beaufort Gyre Observing System
 625 (BGOS; <https://www2.who.edu/site/beaufortgyre/>). The BGOS, a collaborative project
 626 between the Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution (WHOI) in the U.S. and the Institute of
 627 Ocean Sciences (IOS) in Canada, was established in 2003 to measure fresh water and
 628 heat content / fluxes in the BG using moorings, drifting buoys, and remote sensing, with
 629 support from the U.S. National Science Foundation (NSF). In addition to the altimeter and
 630 laser measurements of sea surface height, snow, and sea ice thickness discussed in
 631 section 2.4 below, measurements of sea ice drift and sea surface salinity derived from
 632 scatterometers and radiometers have been helpful to investigate the complex dynamics of
 633 the BG. However, their relatively coarse resolution has limited their application to study
 634 many important ocean and sea ice processes and interactions occurring at mesoscale (e.g.,
 635 Manucharyan et al. 2022). Increasingly, km-scale and sub-daily measurements are in
 636 demand, in part due to the advancement of regional (Maslowski et al. 2012, Maslowski et
 637 al. 2014, Clement Kinney et al. 2022) and global (Wang et al. 2020; Jeong et al. 2023) high-
 638 resolution and process-resolving Earth system models (see Figure 231) accelerated by the
 639 exascale computing capability (<https://www.exascaleproject.org/>). Such high resolution
 640 observations will allow the complex air-sea-ice interactions in the region to be better
 641 quantified, and transports through the narrow gateways between the Arctic and Atlantic
 642 basins to be monitored.

643
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 647

Figure 3. Estimates of the BG freshwater content (in meters) from observations (top; <https://www2.who.edu/site/beaufortgyre/>) and the high-resolution Regional Arctic System Model (RASM; <https://nps.edu/web/rasm>) (bottom), in 1980 (a,d), 2005 (b,e), and 2009 (c,f).

648 **2.4 Arctic Halocline stability**

649 **2.4.1 Nature of tipping point**

650 The vertical stratification in the Arctic Ocean is commonly characterized by a cold halocline
651 (CH) separating a relatively fresh and cold water layer above from the warm and salty
652 Atlantic Water (AW) below (Aagaard et al. 1981). The CH represents a heat sink for the
653 underlying AW and its strength determined by salinity driven vertical density gradient
654 regulates the rate of upward heat release from AW to the surface mixed layer and sea ice.
655 The stability of CH is critical to the presence of the overlying sea ice, as it inhibits deep
656 convection and it partly explains why vertical mixing rates in the upper Arctic Ocean away
657 from steep topography are lower than in midlatitudes (Rippeth et al. 2015). The low mixing
658 rates are also attributed to low tidal energy and sea ice limiting the wind momentum transfer
659 from the atmosphere (Dosser and Rainville 2016).

660 However, changes in the distribution and strength of the CH layer in the Arctic Ocean have
661 been observed in the past. Comparing the submarine hydrographic data from the Scientific
662 Ice Expeditions (SCICEX) in the 1990s against the long-term climatology, Steele and Boyd
663 (1998) revealed the retreat of CH layer from the Amundsen Basin back into the Makarov
664 Basin. This change was attributed to a weakening of the Beaufort High, which in turn
665 resulted in a cyclonic shift of the sea ice Transpolar Drift and freshwater export from the
666 Siberian shelves into the deep basins of the Arctic Ocean (Maslowski et al. 2001). A more
667 recent analysis of the 2002-2015 mooring data from the eastern Eurasian Basin by
668 Polyakov et al. (2020) has shown weakening and shoaling of CH, which was linked to
669 winter convection due to brine rejection during sea ice formation. The decrease of the CH
670 depth in the Eurasian Basin at the rate of -2.5 meters per decade has been recently
671 confirmed by Muilwijk et al. (2023). However, their analysis of observed mean CH depth in
672 the Amerasian basin (or western Arctic) between 1970 and 2018 indicates an opposite,
673 deepening CH depth trend of 7.3 meters per decade (Figure 4). The latter trend could in
674 part be related to the increasing freshwater content in the Beaufort Gyre, as discussed in
675 section 2.3 above, and it emphasises the need to understand critical processes and
676 feedbacks operating in different parts of the Arctic Ocean.

677 Given the observed summer sea ice retreat over the satellite record (Druckenmiller et al.
678 2022), a more efficient and direct air-sea coupling is expected to increase vertical mixing,
679 via generation of surface and internal waves (Liu et al. 2016), and the upward heat flux,
680 thus constituting positive wind-ice-ocean feedback (Fine and Cole 2022). Another positive
681 feedback linked to ice-ocean dynamics relates the thinning (Kwok 2018) and reduced
682 strength (Hibler 1979; Rothrock 1975) of the Arctic sea ice to increased ice drift (Gascard et
683 al. 2008; Rampal et al. 2009), ice-ocean stress, and the upper ocean mixing (McPhee
684 2008). With increased mixing, the heat accumulated in the upper ocean due to summer
685 insolation (Maykut and MCPhee 1995) can be entrained into the surface mixed layer
686 (Maslowski et al. 2012) to reduce ice growth in winter and melt more ice in summer. In both
687 cases, the ice-ocean coupling augments the summer-dominated ice-albedo feedback.

688 Impacts of such dynamically controlled feedbacks have been recently investigated by Beer
689 et al. (2023) using an idealized climate model with varying specified mixing rates for ice-
690 covered and ice-free surface conditions. They find that the wind-ice-ocean feedback can
691 result in a novel bistability in the climate system, which is associated with a hysteresis loop
692 within forced warming and cooling for a limited range of parameters. Furthermore, this
693 study shows that an abrupt tipping point can occur with an irreversible transition to ice-free
694 conditions when crossing the bifurcation point during forced warming. While not conclusive,
695 this study points to the need for improved models of the Arctic and continued and new data
696 to better constrain them and to further investigate potential tipping points associated with
697 the stability of Arctic cold halocline (CH).

698

699 **2.4.2 EO needs and opportunities**

700 One example of EO measurements in support of the CH stability is altimeter data from
 701 polar orbiting missions, i.e., *ERS-1/2*, *Envisat*, and *CryoSat-2*, to measure sea surface
 702 height, snow, and sea ice freeboard/thickness. Their application to investigation of wave
 703 and wind climate in the Arctic Ocean was reported by Liu et al. (2016). However, only
 704 *CryoSat-2* is still active, while well beyond its design lifetime and likely approaching the end
 705 of its mission. Note, that *CryoSat-2* measurements of ice freeboard overlapping the NASA
 706 *IceSat-2* mission, have also allowed improved estimates of snow and sea ice distribution
 707 and thickness in the Arctic Ocean (Kacimi and Kwok 2022). A major challenge for EO
 708 missions is providing a year-long data on the ocean surface (salinity, temperature, height),
 709 sea ice (thickness, deformation, drift) and snow at km and daily-to-weekly timescales.
 710 Hence, future EO high spatial and temporal resolution measurements of the Arctic Ocean
 711 surface, snow, and sea ice are critically needed.

712 In parallel, models of the Arctic Ocean and climate need significant improvements to reduce
 713 persistent biases, especially in representing the coupling across the air-ice-ocean boundary
 714 layer (Maslowski et al. 2012), sea ice thickness distribution (Watts et al. 2021), and the
 715 upper ocean vertical stratification (Shu et al. 2023). Some progress is being made in these
 716 areas in part due to increased spatio-temporal resolution applied to regional Earth System
 717 models (Lee et al. 2023a and 2023b) or global models using unstructured grid with regional
 718 refinements (Veneziani et al. 2022; Wang 2024). However, expanded measurements,
 719 better understanding, and model representation of critical physical processes, for example
 720 involved in shelf-basin exchanges or vertical mixing, are needed and require a combination
 721 of in-situ and remote observations.

722

723

724

725 **Figure 4.** Observed annual mean depth of halocline base in the Eurasian basin (EB; red) and
 726 Amerasian basin (AB; blue) regions (adapted from Figure 1b of Muilwijk et al. 2023).
 727

728

729 **2.5 The Kuroshio large meander – an anomalous state of a multi-stable**
 730 **western boundary current**

731 **2.5.1 Nature of tipping point**

732 Boundary currents are an essential part of the global ocean circulation. Among them,
 733 especially western boundary currents like the Gulf Stream in the North Atlantic and the
 734 Kuroshio in the North Pacific can exhibit a rich variety of spatio-temporal flow patterns due
 735 to their interactions with atmospheric forcing factors in the presence of complex coastlines

736 and bathymetry. At the same time, their pathways impact downstream currents and
737 associated Sea Surface Temperature (SST) patterns (Qiu et al. 2020) with profound
738 impacts on the marine biosphere (Chang et al. 2019, Lizarbe Baretto et al. 2021), ocean-
739 atmosphere heat fluxes and resulting atmospheric processes potentially alternating air
740 temperature, wind and precipitation patterns over large regions.

741 While for many well-studied parts of such boundary currents (e.g. the Gulf Stream and
742 North Atlantic Current), there seems to exist a continuum of possible pathways, the
743 Kuroshio south of Japan presents a rather unique case with a clear clustering of observed
744 current pathways indicating multistability of the regional ocean circulation system.
745 Specifically, extending previous works already starting in the 1960s, Kawabe (1995)
746 suggested the existence of three distinct major pathways of the Kuroshio termed near-
747 shore and off-shore non-large meander and typical large meander (nNLS, oNLS and tLS,
748 respectively). Especially the large meander state with its recirculation gyre and enclosed
749 cold-surface water anomaly has attracted great interest during the last decades due to its
750 complex dynamics and relevance for the climate and marine biosphere around the
751 Japanese islands. The existence of discrete states opens the possibility of a discontinuous
752 response to external forcing such as climate change; however the research reported here
753 represents attempts to understand these inherently discrete states of the system, which is a
754 pre-requisite for anticipating climate change responses.

755 Between 1950 and present-day, eight Kuroshio large meander events took place at
756 apparently random occurrence times (Qiu and Chen, 2021) and with a broad distribution of
757 lifetimes of the large meander state, the latest being the longest on record and continuing
758 since August 2017. By combining sea-surface height (SSH) observations from satellite
759 altimetry with reanalysis based surface wind stress patterns and comparing the recent
760 patterns with the conditions during the previous (2004-2005) large meander event, Qiu et
761 al. (2023) attributed the unusual stability of the ongoing event to an exceptionally stable
762 dynamic state of the Kuroshio Extension, which minimizes the westward propagation of
763 eddies, potentially destabilizing the upstream Kuroshio path while in parallel fostering the
764 maintenance of the recirculation gyre.

765 *Impacts*

766 The presence of a Kuroshio large meander has a profound impact on the climate conditions
767 in the Northwest Pacific region around Japan. Sugimoto et al. (2021) reported marked
768 coastal warming during summer off the Kanto-Tokai district of Japan during the present
769 large meander. Using a regional atmospheric model, they could show that a warming of the
770 near-coastal surface waters in the wake of the recirculation gyre leads to an increase of
771 water vapour in the low-level atmosphere due to enhanced evaporation near the coast.
772 Along with altered near-surface winds this results in a net increase of downward longwave
773 radiation over the Kanto region and, hence, increasingly hot and humid summers. By
774 contrast, for winter conditions during the large meander event of 2004-05, Xu et al. (2010)
775 already reported reduced winds and precipitation resulting from the cool water pool
776 between the Kuroshio and the Japanese coast. In general, the cool water pool along with
777 coastal warming off the Tokai province of Japan appears as a common fingerprint of large
778 meander events (Sugimoto et al., 2019). Other related effects of the wintertime presence of
779 a Kuroshio large meander include a southward shift of primary extratropical cyclone tracks
780 along with reduced latent heat fluxes south of Japan (Nakamura et al., 2012; Hayasaki et
781 al., 2013). Based on regional climate modelling, Murazaki et al. (2015) showed that the cold
782 SST anomaly of the large meander consistently leads to reduced upward surface turbulent
783 heat flux, lower precipitation frequency, and less frequent steep horizontal gradients in
784 equivalent potential temperature over the ocean during both summer and winter.

785 In addition to its pivotal effects on regional atmospheric processes, the presence of a
786 Kuroshio large meander also exerts direct influence on ocean dynamics, resulting in distinct

787 patterns of eddy kinetic energy, potential vorticity, relative vorticity, and eddy-mean flow
788 interaction south of Japan (Ma, 2019). Based on a new multi-scale statistical analysis tool,
789 Yang and Liang (2019) identified a spatially coherent inverse cascade of kinetic energy
790 from synoptic eddies to the slowly varying mean flow over the whole large meander region,
791 along with a particular relevance of an initial influx of mesoscale eddy energy from
792 upstream regions responsible for the emergence of the inverse cascade. In another study,
793 Qiu and Chen (2021) identified intense anticyclonic eddies emanating from the Subtropical
794 Counter-Current interacting with Kuroshio path perturbations southeast of Kyushu,
795 generating positive relative vorticity along the coast finally leading to the formation of the
796 large meander. Not surprisingly, the reported effects on ocean circulation at various spatial
797 and temporal scales can also have a profound impact on biological and biogeochemical
798 processes in the Northwest Pacific (Hayashida et al., 2023).

799

800 **2.5.2 EO needs and opportunities**

801 From the aforementioned results, it may be noted that especially the turbulent flow patterns
802 in the adjacent Pacific Ocean south of Japan are crucial for understanding the processes
803 leading to the formation and maintenance of the Kuroshio large meander. While
804 atmospheric impacts can be well traced with state of the art *in situ* and remote sensing
805 based products, the importance of upscale kinetic energy transfer from synoptic scales
806 (Yang and Liang 2019) points to a particular area high-frequency EO data (SST, sea
807 surface height SSH, and potentially SSS, on timescales shorter than 15 days, and
808 especially in near-coastal regions) is important to fully quantify the dynamics preceding the
809 emergence of a large meander. Based on such improved real-time observational datasets
810 along with better process understanding (generated by exploiting physics-based models
811 and/or modern artificial intelligence methods), forecasts of future state transitions of the
812 Kuroshio path and its regional climatic impacts could potentially be developed at societally
813 relevant lead times.

814 **2.6 Ocean deoxygenation**

815 **2.6.1 Nature of tipping point**

816 With progressing global warming there is an increased risk that climate-relevant
817 biogeochemical ocean elements might cross critical thresholds and tip into novel states, with
818 severe consequences for the climate system, marine ecosystems and human societies
819 (Heinze et al. 2021, Rockstrom et al., 2009, Lenton et al., 2008). Among the biogeochemical
820 elements that may undergo large and possibly irreversible (on human time scales) changes
821 in response to the ongoing anthropogenic perturbations is the ocean oxygen (O₂) content,
822 with potentially large effects on marine biogeochemistry and ecosystems (Watson 2016;
823 Rockstrom et al., 2009, Lenton et al., 2008, Heinze et al. 2021). The oceanic O₂ content has
824 undergone large variations throughout the earth's history, driving the evolution of novel
825 metabolic pathways that shaped ocean biogeochemistry as we see it today (Canfield et al.,
826 2010). Dissolved O₂ is necessary for sustaining aerobic life in the ocean and regulates redox-
827 sensitive biogeochemical processes. The cycling of O₂ is strongly linked with the nitrogen (N),
828 phosphorus (P), iron (Fe) and the carbon (C) cycles. Changes in oxygen will impact the
829 cycling of any of the other elements and can potentially lead to an amplification/reduction of
830 the initial perturbation, with stabilizing or destabilizing feedbacks to the climate system.

831 Currently, ocean warming is affecting the oceanic dissolved oxygen content. Oxygen
832 concentrations have decreased by about 2% over the last 50 years (Ito, et al., 2017;
833 Schmidtko et al., 2017), a process termed ocean deoxygenation. Tropical Oxygen Deficient
834 Zones (ODZs), where oxygen concentrations fall below values critical for the onset of the

835 anaerobic microbial processes and/or have sublethal effects (hypoxia) on animals, are
836 expanding (Stramma et al., 2008). These oxygen changes are due to a combination of
837 chemical, physical and biological drivers (Bopp et al., 2017; Oschlies et al., 2018) and show
838 a significant regional and depth variability (Ito et al., 2017). The reduction in temperature-
839 dependent O₂ solubility is well quantified and estimated to account only for about 15% of the
840 observed oceanic global O₂ loss (Helm et al., 2011). The contribution from changes in
841 circulation and associated reduced ventilation is less certain, potentially explaining the
842 majority of the deep ocean O₂ changes (Breitburg et al., 2018). O₂ consumption due to
843 biological respiration is reduced in the low-latitude nutrient-limited regions that experience
844 reduced productivity, but enhanced in high-latitude regions where biological production has
845 intensified under global warming (Laufkötter et al., 2015, 2016; Steinacher et al., 2010).

846 Next to uncertainty of driving processes, detectability of climate-driven O₂ trends is
847 challenged by natural short-term variability of oxygen (Frölicher et al., 2009; Long et al., 2016;
848 Bopp et al., 2017) and poor spatiotemporal coverage of O₂ observations (Grégoire et al.,
849 2021). The time required for anthropogenically forced signals to emerge above background
850 noise (time of emergence) is found to be regionally variable. Longer timescales are required
851 in regions where processes cause compensating effects (compensation of the thermal and
852 non-thermal (biological productivity and ventilation) changes), with a resulting net weak trend
853 (Bopp et al., 2017) such as in the tropical regions (Cabre et al., 2015). Model projections
854 suggest that while stopping CO₂ emissions will stop ocean surface warming and near surface
855 ocean deoxygenation, the deep ocean layers are expected to continue losing oxygen for
856 centuries (Oschlies et al., 2021, Frölicher et al., 2020). This committed deoxygenation results
857 from the reduced solubility of warm deep waters that have been last in contact with the
858 atmosphere during the high CO₂ emission era, and the longer ventilation ages in the ocean
859 interior due to the weakened overturning circulation inertia (Oschlies et al., 2021). However,
860 high uncertainties exist if current steady ocean deoxygenation can evolve into abrupt
861 widespread O₂ loss over human timescales (centennial).

862 Paleoclimate records indicate that widespread ocean deoxygenation events, known as
863 Oceanic anoxic events (OAEs), associated with profound geochemical changes, occurred
864 multiple times during the Earth's history (Jenkyns, 2010). The occurrence of these events
865 has generally been associated with an abrupt temperature rise induced by rapid atmospheric
866 CO₂ increase (eg. by volcanic activity) and associated reduced O₂ solubility, ocean circulation
867 changes and, on time scales longer than 100000 years, enhanced continental nutrient
868 weathering (Kiehl and Shields, 2005). It is hypothesised that amplification by positive
869 biogeochemical feedbacks such as phosphorus (Jenkyns, 2010; Monterio et al., 2012;
870 Watson et al., 2017) or iron (Fe) sediment regeneration (Wallmann et al., 2019), from low-
871 oxygen sediments, is required to further boost the biological demand of oxygen, and meet
872 the conditions for wide-spread OAEs. Characteristics of localized ODZs (nowadays in the
873 tropical low latitude ocean basins) have changed over time. ODZs expanded and contracted
874 not only over millennial but also on shorter, centennial and decadal timescales in response
875 to ocean ventilation changes, due to climate fluctuations (Jaccard and Galbraith, 2012;
876 Galbraith et al., 2013) and natural variability (Stramma et al., 2020; Segschneider et al.,
877 2018), and ecological shifts that control the depth of organic particle remineralization (Lu et
878 al. 2018, Hülse et al. 2021, Crichton et al. 2023). Continental configuration is also thought to
879 influence the sensitivity of the ocean system to biogeochemical feedbacks (Monteiro et al.
880 2012, Meyer et al. 2008).

881 Currently the drivers, the sign of change and time scale of O₂ tipping are not well known
882 (Armstrong McKay et al. 2022). The projected O₂ decline under global warming scenarios is
883 found to rebound within several thousand years in multi-millennial model studies due to
884 circulation reinvigoration (Yamamoto et al., 2015; Frölicher et al., 2020) or to lagged
885 responses in biogeochemical feedbacks (Oschlies et al., 2019; Kvale et al., 2019). O₂ tipping

886 behaviour has emerged in modelling studies associated with the weakening of the
887 overturning circulation, under past atmospheric and/or orbital forcings over millennial
888 timescales (Pohl et al. 2021, Segschneider et al., 2018, Brown and Galbraith, 2016;
889 Schmittner et al., 2007), changes to continental configuration (Pohl et al. 2022), and from
890 complex biogeochemical feedbacks, both in box-models (Watson et al., 2017, Wallmann et
891 al., 2005, 2019, 2022; Handoh and Lenton 2003) and in intermediate-complexity Earth
892 system model (ESM) experiments (Kemena et al., 2019; Niemeyer et al., 2017, Lu et al. 2018,
893 Meyer et al. 2008, Hülse et al. 2021, Crichton et al. 2021, Frölicher et al. 2020.). However, a
894 comprehensive assessment of the potential physical and biogeochemical drivers of tipping
895 behaviour in ocean oxygen is lacking. This is mostly due to the limited knowledge of key
896 biochemical complexity and elevated computational costs of long-times scale (centennial to
897 multi-millennial) modelling experiments. As such, our understanding and ability to identify the
898 potentially tipping behaviour of O₂ is currently limited.

899 *Drivers and timescales*

900 More than 99% of all of the molecular oxygen on the planet is in the atmosphere with less
901 than 1% being dissolved in the ocean (Oschlies, 2019). The oceanic O₂ content is supplied
902 by uptake from the atmosphere at the surface ocean, mostly driven by O₂ temperature-
903 dependent solubility and ocean circulation that transports cold surface O₂-rich waters into the
904 ocean interior during deep water formation at high latitudes. Dissolved O₂ is lost in the
905 ocean by biological consumption via biological respiration. Factors that affect O₂ solubility,
906 ocean circulation and biological oxygen consumption can drive ocean deoxygenation (Figure
907 5) and trigger O₂ tipping behaviour.

908 *Physical-chemical Drivers*

909 In model simulations a general pattern emerges on millennial timescales that is consistent
910 with paleo proxy data. Under cold climates, such as the Last Glacial Maximum, the reduction
911 in deep water formation leads to an increasingly separated well-oxygenated upper ocean and
912 a poorly ventilated oxygen-depleted deep ocean (Jaccard and Galbraith, 2012; Somes et al.,
913 2017; Pohl et al. 2021). Under warming climates, ocean surface warming leads to a reduction
914 of O₂ solubility and to the intensification of stratification and slow-down of circulation and
915 vertical mixing, resulting in subsurface ocean deoxygenation and widespread oxygen
916 depletion (Tsandev and Slomp, 2009; Ruvalcaba Baroni et al., 2014).

917 *Biogeochemical feedbacks*

918 It is still a matter of debate whether the climate forcing exerted by volcanic CO₂ emissions,
919 was sufficient to explain the aerial extent of ocean anoxia during past OAE or if additional
920 feedbacks were required to amplify the deoxygenation trend induced by global warming
921 (Jenkyns, 2010; Wallmann et al., 2019). Phosphorus is a key nutrient for supporting biological
922 production. This nutrient is generally provided to the ocean by continental weathering and is
923 removed from the ocean by being incorporated in marine sediments. However, if bottom
924 water O₂ concentrations fall below a certain threshold level this element can be released from
925 sediments back into the water (Van Cappellen and Ingall, 1994), where it can fertilise organic
926 matter production and remineralization (Beil et al., 2020; Jenkyns et al., 2010, Watson et
927 al., 2017). Despite large uncertainties regarding the weathering and sedimentary P fluxes
928 model parameterizations, recent modelling studies have shown that enhanced ocean P fluxes
929 from weathering and/or from anoxic sediments, under present, future (Niemeyer et al., 2017;
930 Kemena, et al., 2019) and past climate scenarios (Wallmann, 2005; Monteiro et al., 2012),
931 can promote additional ocean productivity. This in turn, exerts a positive feedback on
932 deoxygenation, leading to a large increase in the volume of OD₂ on millennial timescales.
933 The large expansion of suboxia then causes a net loss of bioavailable N that is consumed
934 during organic matter remineralization in OD₂ in the process of denitrification. Eventually,
935 in a negative feedback, a considerable amount of P is left unused in the ocean as N becomes
936 the primary nutrient limiting biological productivity (and is not compensated for by the Fe-

937 limited N₂ fixers) thus ultimately constraining the expansion of ODZ (Kemena et al., 2019).
938 Hence, although P addition to the ocean drives additional deoxygenation, the positive redox-
939 related feedback on benthic P release is eventually limited by the availability of N and the
940 apparent inability of N₂ fixers to respond to the larger P inventory. Further, the inability of N₂
941 fixers to respond to denitrification allows, in current models that tend to suppress N₂ fixation
942 in low temperature regions, for a net ocean O₂ accumulation in a multi-millennial Earth
943 System Model (ESM) simulation (Oschlies et al., 2019). Models without the full representation
944 of the N-cycle feedbacks, miss this important negative feedback limiting global deoxygenation
945 (Wallmann, 2003).

946 On the other hand, how a full dynamic iron cycle in an Earth system model will affect the
947 utilisation of the added P by N₂ fixers remains to be tested. In such a model setting, primary
948 production is not limited by N-loss and widespread deoxygenation can be self-sustained
949 (Landolfi et al., 2013). Positive feedbacks between sedimentary P and Fe release and ODZ
950 intensification could potentially drive a widespread and lasting expansion of oxygen-depleted
951 ocean regions on centennial timescales, eventually leading to euxinic events (Canfield,
952 2006). This is shown in a recent regional box-model study of the Eastern Tropical Pacific.
953 Under current warming conditions if the Fe-demand of N₂ fixing organisms can be met by O₂-
954 dependent sedimentary Fe release, a positive feedback loop develops on decadal timescales
955 and amplifies O₂ decline (Wallmann et al., 2022). As N losses are not compensated for by N₂
956 fixation due to stoichiometric constraints (Landolfi et al., 2013), NO₃ and NO₂ can become
957 depleted and sulfidic conditions may eventually occur (Wallmann et al., 2019, 2022). The
958 production of hydrogen sulfide (a gas toxic to animals) may be limited by the consumption of
959 sulfide-oxidizing photoautotrophs (Meyer et al. 2008) and by the scavenging of it by organic
960 particles, which can help to reoxygenate the ocean after an OAE and reduce atmospheric
961 CO₂ concentrations by efficiently sequestering biological carbon and providing an alkalinity
962 source (Hülse et al. 2019). The release of H₂S in euxinic conditions is supported by
963 paleorecords and remains a suspected mass extinction mechanism (Meyer et al 2008). The
964 potential for negative H₂S feedbacks to prevent widespread deoxygenation of the water
965 column is not well constrained.

966 It is unclear whether the burning of fossil fuels combined with human activities delivering
967 additional nutrients, from atmospheric deposition and/or river-discharge and land-use
968 changes, are sufficient to trigger such positive biogeochemical feedbacks (e.g. from
969 increased stratification and associated reduced interior ocean ventilation, in interplay with
970 increased phosphorus input from fertilisers-use, accelerated weathering, land-use changes,
971 and/or recycling from sediments under anoxic conditions), if they could lead to a widespread
972 deoxygenation and over which timescales. Given the large uncertainties over drivers,
973 mechanisms, time-scale and critical thresholds for triggering a widespread oxygen loss,
974 ocean deoxygenation is currently regarded as an uncertain potential tipping element and has
975 not been included within the core tipping elements by the recent study of Armstrong McKay
976 et al., 2022.

977 What is more, ESM models predict only about half of the ocean deoxygenation that is
978 currently observed (Oschlies et al., 2018), suggesting that current models may lack key
979 physical and biogeochemical feedback mechanisms that amplify the respiratory oxygen
980 demand in the ocean interior (Oschlies et al., 2018). Models that include positive feedbacks
981 between anoxia, phosphorus and/or Fe recycling from sediments and marine productivity
982 have been shown to exhibit a non-linear behaviour, tipping into widespread deoxygenation
983 on centennial to millennial timescales (Kemena et al., 2019; Wallmann et al., 2019; Somes et
984 al., 2017). These studies emphasise the critical role of biogeochemical feedbacks in affecting
985 the ocean O₂ content that need to be accounted for in models for past and future projections.

986 *Biological-Ecosystem Impacts of tipping*

987 Ocean deoxygenation poses a serious direct threat to life in the ocean. Under low oxygen
988 conditions ($< 62 \text{ mmol m}^{-3}$, hypoxia) metabolic processes such as respiration, reproduction
989 and movement may be impaired (Rabalais et al., 2010). At ecosystem level this will lead to
990 changes in community structure towards hypoxia-tolerant species of fish and invertebrates,
991 habitat compression, migration and mass mortality (Breitburg et al., 2018). Species
992 extirpation (local species loss) can occur when ecophysiological tolerances of temperature
993 and O_2 threshold are crossed. These can be quantified from the local O_2 -supply to demand
994 ratio (Penn et al. 2019). On a global scale, species extinction can occur when habitat loss
995 exceeds a critical ocean fraction. In a model study extirpation risk has been found to be higher
996 in the high latitude and the tropics under a high emission scenario. Extirpation, an ecological
997 tipping point, is likely to culminate in a mass extinction similar to those in Earth's past by the
998 end of the 21st century under continued global warming (Penn and Deutsch, 2022).

999 *Biogeochemical-Climatic Impacts of tipping*

1000 The expansion of $\text{OD} > Z$ ($< 5 \text{ mmol m}^{-3}$, suboxia) will restrict aerobic remineralization and
1001 trigger anaerobic microbial processes, which affect the cycling of elements nitrogen,
1002 phosphorus, iron, sulfur and various trace metals, and the production of greenhouse gases
1003 such as nitrous oxide (N_2O) and methane (CH_4). Under low O_2 conditions, the anaerobic
1004 microbially-driven remineralization of organic matter will proceed consuming nitrate,
1005 manganese and iron oxides and sulphate sequentially. The consumption of NO_3 via the
1006 microbial processes of denitrification and anammox can increase. These microbial processes
1007 result in the loss of fixed N, that if compensated regionally for by N_2 fixation may lead to
1008 positive feedbacks and self-sustained $\text{OD} > Z$ expansion (Landolfi et al., 2013) and euxinia
1009 may develop (Canfield, 2006). During denitrification and nitrification under low O_2 conditions,
1010 the production of N_2O occurs (Ward and Jansen, 2014). This potent greenhouse gas, if
1011 released to the atmosphere, has the potential to amplify global warming and deoxygenation,
1012 constituting a positive feedback. Ocean deoxygenation also leads to major changes in the
1013 redox-sensitive cycling of essential elements and metals such as P and Fe. Sediment release
1014 of these elements can occur under low bottom water oxygen concentrations (Van Cappellen
1015 and Ingall, 1994; Dale et al., 2015), potentially stimulating organic matter production and
1016 remineralization, thereby also exerting positive feedback on deoxygenation (Walmann et al.,
1017 2019).

1018 **2.6.2 EO needs and opportunities**

1019 *Monitoring*

1020 Since ocean deoxygenation can cause severe ecosystem disruptions and feedbacks to other
1021 elements and climate, the availability of early warning systems, in open and coastal ocean is
1022 highly desirable. The identification of changes and possible TPs in ocean O_2 requires
1023 adequately long observational records with adequate spatial coverage. Although novel
1024 technologies have largely expanded the O_2 observing system (Grégoire et al., 2021), with O_2
1025 sensors routinely deployed on a range of *in situ* platforms (such as ARGO, AUVs and gliders,
1026 moorings) that allow the assessment of intraseasonal, seasonal and interannual oxygen
1027 variability, challenges remain for identifying long-term trends. The use of EO observations
1028 such as temperature (SST), ocean productivity (Ocean Color), combined through artificial
1029 intelligence to reconstruct oxygen changes, can provide novel avenues towards monitoring
1030 and early warning systems over the satellite era. Of elevated interest for this purpose is the
1031 remotely sensed data of chlorophyll a (Chla) a phytoplankton biomass proxy, particulate back
1032 scattering (bbp) a proxy for non algal particulate material, a the derived quantity particulate
1033 organic carbon (POC) and their 3D reconstruction, and more widespread availability of
1034 HYPER-spectral remote sensing reflectances (Rrs), complemented with field measurements
1035 and new *in situ* observing systems (like BGC-Argo) of key variables such as O_2 and nutrients.
1036 Of crucial importance are also observational constraints on ocean circulation and its changes
1037 over time. Abiotic transient tracers can be particularly valuable to provide information about

1038 changes in ventilation and residence times over which respiratory signals can accumulate in
1039 the ocean interior. Detection of fingerprints of ocean deoxygenation such as N₂O and H₂S
1040 fluxes at the sea surface via remote sensing (Infrared Atmospheric Sounding Interferometer,
1041 IASI) also represent potential avenues that require further development (Garcia et al., 2018).

1042 *Paleoproxies*

1043 The reconstruction of regional O₂ levels of the past ocean relies on the indirect evidence of
1044 O₂ dynamics from local sedimentary proxy data such as benthic foraminifera, redox-sensitive
1045 elements, and isotopic fingerprints. Further efforts towards expanding sparse paleoproxy
1046 datasets, improving the resolution of paleo data, providing uncertainty estimates in the paleo-
1047 reconstructions are required to advance our quantitative understanding of OAE and
1048 attribution of their drivers and enhance our predictive capabilities

1049 *Modelling*

1050 ESMs are powerful tools to explore the possibility of ocean O₂ tipping over a range of
1051 timescales and forcings. The drivers, location and likelihood of tipping are sensitive to
1052 emerging physical and biogeochemical feedbacks (Figure 5). However, biogeochemical
1053 processes are poorly constrained and are not fully represented in current state-of-the-art
1054 models. A multimodel intercomparison experiment which included key biogeochemical
1055 processes (Figure 5) would be desirable to test mechanisms of oxygen tipping in models of
1056 different complexities. This effort could potentially build from the TipMIP programme
1057 (<https://tipmip.pik-potsdam.de/>), and specifically designed to tackle the following questions:

- 1058 ● What are the drivers, key physical processes and biogeochemical feedbacks, associated
1059 with oxygen tipping behaviour?
- 1060 ● What are the characteristic spatial and temporal scales of positive and negative
1061 feedbacks and what is their combined effect on ocean oxygen?
- 1062 ● What are the drivers' tipping points and thresholds and what are their corresponding
1063 uncertainties?
- 1064 ● What is the risk of crossing individual TPs, at different levels of ongoing climate and land-
1065 use change, which might trigger oxygen tipping behaviour?
- 1066 ● Are the respective O₂ changes abrupt and on which timescales are they reversible?

1067 How is the overall stability of the Earth system affected by marine deoxygenation?

1068 Remotely sensed data can further help to constrain biogeochemical processes in climate
1069 models, thereby reducing uncertainties in the thresholds of drivers and timescales of climate
1070 tipping elements.

1071

1072 **Figure 5.** Schematics of the physical, chemical and biogeochemical processes that interact and
 1073 impact ocean oxygen content over multiple timescales. Red arrows represent positive feedbacks,
 1074 blue arrows represent negative feedbacks. The anthropogenic climate perturbation affects O₂
 1075 solubility, ventilation and biological O₂ consumption (grey arrows) potentially with positive or
 1076 negative feedbacks. With warming O₂ solubility is reduced and, via changes in stratification and
 1077 mixing, ocean ventilation declines. The decline in surface nutrient supply due to enhanced
 1078 stratification affects marine productivity generally with a decline in the tropics and increase in the
 1079 high latitudes. The net effect is uncertain and may lead to expansion of oxygen minimum zone on
 1080 decadal to centennial timescales, where anoxic microbial processes, denitrification and anammox,
 1081 can lead to N loss and the production of the greenhouse gas N₂O. A negative feedback can occur
 1082 if N loss is not compensated for by N₂ fixation with the potential to lead to a collapse of marine
 1083 productivity on the one hand and O₂ accumulation as organic matter is respired anaerobically.
 1084 However, If N fixation is promoted by sedimentary release of P and Fe and/or P weathering, a self-
 1085 sustained positive feedback can occur, potentially leading to N runaway and eventually the
 1086 establishment of euxinia.

1087

1088 Overall, our current scientific knowledge on the tipping behaviour of ocean oxygen is limited,
 1089 a systematic analysis, drawing from expanded current and paleoproxy observations and
 1090 multimodel ensemble studies, is desirable. Further development may consider: (i) Expanding
 1091 spatial and temporal coverage of multiplatform observations of O₂ and associated variables,
 1092 particularly those informing about ocean ventilation and changes in ventilation (e.g. abiotic
 1093 transient tracers); (ii) Testing the use of artificial intelligence (AI) tools to exploit ever growing
 1094 EO-observations for O₂ studies (iii) Expanding the sedimentary record and using multivariate
 1095 approaches for attribution studies (iv) Testing mechanisms of oxygen tipping in models of
 1096 different complexities.

1097 In addressing these questions, critical knowledge gaps in the oceanic O₂ controls will be
 1098 reduced and understanding of Earth system homeostasis will be improved.

1099

1100 **3. Tipping Points in Pelagic Marine Ecosystems**

1101 In the dynamic expanse of the ocean, pelagic organisms, inhabitants of the water column,
1102 exhibit continual movement—both vertically and horizontally—engaging in drifting,
1103 swimming, and migrating activities. Consequently, conventional time series measurement
1104 systems conducted over fixed grids, such as repeated transects, only offer an approximate
1105 representation of the temporal dynamics of observed species. The inherent limitation lies in
1106 our fixed spatial sampling scale, which fails to align with the fluid variability of the samples.
1107 Organisms may be missed during sampling, yet reside slightly deeper or a few meters or
1108 kilometres away in any direction, and their presence can be overestimated because of their
1109 typically patchy distribution. Moreover, the uncertainty extends to the entities being
1110 sampled—be it individuals, populations, or species—making it challenging to ascertain
1111 whether the population measured at time 't' is the same as that observed at time 't+n'.

1112 Consequently, there exists a significant contrast between time series studies of pelagic
1113 organisms freely moving in three dimensions in the water column, and benthic organisms
1114 inhabiting the seafloor and moving in two dimensions with reduced mobility. The former
1115 incorporate spatial and temporal uncertainties that are challenging to measure accurately,
1116 while the latter provides relatively precise spatial and temporal measurements, particularly
1117 for sessile species, offering a degree of population certainty.

1118 Despite numerous studies addressing sampling design and uncertainty in each
1119 compartment (Pepin and Helbig 2012, Lin et al. 2010, van Hoey et al. 2019), to our
1120 knowledge the inherent difference between these compartments has not been thoroughly
1121 assessed.

1122 There has been extensive research on marine benthos tipping points and phase shifts (this
1123 is the term commonly used in benthos research, while regime shifts or abrupt shift are the
1124 terms commonly used in water column research). Thus, the challenges faced by coral
1125 reefs, a global concern among ecologists, are well-documented (Hughes 1994, Matz et al.
1126 2018). Numerous studies explore phase shift and tipping point dynamics leading to the
1127 transition of coral reefs to alternative algal states, and several provide future projections,
1128 and reef-danger warnings based on earth observations (Nim et al. 2010, Claar et al. 2020,
1129 Hobday et al. 2023, Wernberg et al. 2023, Melet et al. 2020, Heron et al. 2016). Due to their
1130 role as biodiversity hotspots, nursery grounds, nutrient cycling hubs, and CO₂ sequestering
1131 agents, coral reefs are considered a 'tipping element' in various works (Lenton et al. 2008,
1132 Armstrong McKay et al. 2022, Wang et al. 2023).

1133 In contrast, the pelagic ocean organisms, invisible and un-gridded, moving and mixing in
1134 three dimensions, have not yet been recognized as a tipping element. The 3D moving
1135 matrix complicates the identification of pelagic ecological shifts (often referred to as abrupt
1136 shifts), which are not marked by clear irreversibility, a crucial concept in defining tipping
1137 points. Nevertheless, shifts in these interconnected and interchanging systems can have
1138 potential global-scale consequences, and research has indicated that pelagic shifts can
1139 synchronously occur in distant oceanic basins and that the frequency and magnitude of the
1140 shifts may increase as the earth system continues to warm (Beaugrand et al, 2015;
1141 Beaugrand et al 2019).

1142 This section, therefore, concentrates on abrupt shifts and tipping points in the pelagic
1143 components of the ocean, emphasising the potential of EO to monitor their temporal and
1144 spatial dynamics and provide early warnings. All pelagic components described in this
1145 section exhibit threshold behaviour and possess the potential to impact biological elements

1146 (such as the food web) and even contribute feedback to the climate (e.g., phytoplankton),
1147 making them 'invisible' tipping elements.

1148 The pelagic component, particularly the plankton community, plays a vital role in sustaining
1149 life on Earth. Phytoplankton, forming the foundation of marine food webs, contribute to
1150 approximately half of the global primary production. Additionally, through various processes
1151 and interactions (e.g., carbon sequestration, biological pump, aerosol/DMS production,
1152 ocean albedo, oceanic uptake of heat), they influence temperature, ocean acidity, carbon
1153 cycling, and the overall climate system (Miloslavich et al. 2018). Marine zooplankton,
1154 sustained by phytoplankton, encompass a diverse range of species, including copepods,
1155 krill, and jellyfish, along with the larval stages of most marine animals. Each plays a specific
1156 role in nutrient cycling and ecosystem stability, holding immense ecological and economic
1157 importance in marine ecosystems. Their impact extends to human societies, significantly
1158 contributing to multiple economic sectors. Fisheries and farmed seafood, sustained by
1159 plankton, provide a significant source of animal protein to more than 3 billion people
1160 globally, with the total first sale value of global production estimated at USD 406 billion in
1161 2020 (of which USD 141 billion for capture fisheries and USD 265 billion for aquaculture,
1162 FAO 2022).

1163 Presently, human activities exert a profound impact on marine life at scales ranging from
1164 global to local, including global warming, acidification, deoxygenation, overfishing, pollution,
1165 and notably, the burgeoning issue of plastics. If current trends persist, the weight of plastics
1166 in the world's oceans is projected to surpass that of fish by 2050 (Industry Agenda 2016).
1167 All these factors, individually or in combination, can propel marine communities towards
1168 ecological shifts.

1169 The *pelagic tipping point dilemma* thus revolves around the vital task of identifying tipping
1170 points and ecological shifts in a vast, dynamic ecosystem. The inherent challenges stem
1171 from its vastness, spanning regional to semi-global scales, its dynamic 3D nature, and its
1172 interconnectedness with other biological and physical components of the Earth system.
1173 Thus, the potential consequences of tipping points in the pelagic ecosystem are far-
1174 reaching, surpassing the confines of specific habitats or areas. Early warnings of hard-to-
1175 identify critical changes (including dimension, intensity and pace of the changes) are
1176 consequently *crucial* and *complex* because of the inherent mismatch between sampling
1177 design and sampled population.

1178 Satellite observations offer a promising avenue in addressing this dilemma. Their extensive
1179 scope and comprehensive coverage make a substantial contribution to this quest. These
1180 observations provide consistent, and in some cases decade-long, monitoring on a global
1181 scale. While they may be limited in the depth dimension, satellite observations excel in
1182 providing excellent horizontal coverage. This capability accommodates regions with diverse
1183 requirements, resources, and monitoring capabilities, offering valuable insights into the
1184 elusive open ocean.

1185

1186 **3.1 Phytoplankton productivity and DMS-phytoplankton-cloud interactions**

1187 **3.1.1 Nature of tipping point**

1188 *Unpredictable abrupt shifts during the 21st century*

1189 Marine phytoplankton, constituting half of the global net primary production, play a pivotal
1190 role in sustaining the Earth's Biosphere (Field et al., 1998). Their productivity and diversity
1191 in the ocean control the bottom-up dynamics of crucial commercial seafood products,
1192 influencing the magnitude and pathways of energy transfer within the marine food web. In a
1193 prior review on tipping elements in marine ecosystems (Section 2.2 of Swingedouw et al.,

1194 2020), the remote sensing of chlorophyll-a for monitoring phytoplankton was recognized as
1195 an advanced and accessible Earth Observation tool for marine ecosystems.

1196 Satellite ocean colour sensors have continuously provided information on the global
1197 distribution of surface phytoplankton biomass and community composition since the late
1198 1990s (Groom et al., 2019). This information has unveiled global-scale changes, including
1199 the expansion of the oligotrophic ocean (ocean desertification) and phenological shifts in
1200 seasonal blooms which can have substantial consequences for higher trophic levels
1201 (Section 2.2.4 of Swingedouw et al., 2020).

1202 A notable recent application of remote sensing to phytoplankton involves the development
1203 and use of an advanced lower trophic level marine ecosystem model. This model
1204 incorporates 35 phytoplankton groups based on various functional types and size classes
1205 (Dutkiewicz et al., 2021), offering a more comprehensive representation of phytoplankton
1206 diversity compared to current-generation Earth System models, which typically include only
1207 1-3 phytoplankton groups (Kearney et al., 2021). Advances in ocean colour sensors and
1208 algorithms have allowed the estimation of sea surface chlorophyll-a concentration for
1209 different size classes (e.g., Ward, 2015), contributing to a better understanding of the global
1210 distribution of the simulated phytoplankton community structure in recent decades
1211 (Dutkiewicz et al., 2021).

1212 A global climate projection utilising the 35-compartment phytoplankton model under a high
1213 greenhouse gas emission scenario illustrates potential abrupt shifts in phytoplankton
1214 biomass, productivity, and community structure across various oceanic regions during the
1215 latter half of the 21st century (Cael et al., 2021). These shifts may exceed 50% relative to
1216 historical baselines, covering up to 25% of the tropics and subtropical gyres (Cael et al.,
1217 2021). Notably, these abrupt shifts are anticipated on species requiring specific resources
1218 like diatoms, dinoflagellates, and diazotrophs (Dutkiewicz et al., 2020), particularly in
1219 subtropical regions (Cael et al., 2021). Importantly, these shifts occur independently of
1220 gradual changes in environmental variables, such as temperature and nutrients, making
1221 them unpredictable using standard early warning signals (Cael et al., 2021).

1222 The causes of these abrupt shifts are unclear, but their occurrence at the edges of
1223 subtropical gyres suggests a potential link to the expansion of ocean deserts (Cael et al.,
1224 2021; Karl et al., 1995). Whether these shifts are reversible or not remains an open
1225 question that requires projections beyond the 21st century. Nevertheless, such abrupt shifts
1226 could trigger cascading effects in higher trophic levels and biogeochemical cycles due to
1227 the strong coupling of these systems. Investigating these consequences can be achieved
1228 by incorporating outputs from phytoplankton diversity models (e.g., Cael et al., 2021) into
1229 higher trophic level marine ecosystem models (e.g., Tittensor et al., 2021). This integrative
1230 approach represents a step towards understanding ecosystem changes comprehensively.
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1232 *Impacts: implications for dimethylsulfide*

1233 Abrupt shifts in phytoplankton productivity and diversity carry significant implications for the
1234 phytoplankton-aerosol-cloud feedback mediated by dimethylsulfide (DMS), as proposed by
1235 Charlson et al. (1987). DMS, a marine biogenic source of sulfur-containing aerosols such
1236 as sulfate, plays a key role in influencing the radiative properties of the atmosphere. For
1237 instance, a projected 24% reduction in the global sea-to-air DMS flux, potentially resulting
1238 from substantial changes in phytoplankton productivity and diversity, is estimated to warm
1239 the atmosphere by up to 0.76 K globally (Six et al., 2013). In the ocean, DMS originates
1240 from dimethylsulfoniopropionate (DMSP), an organosulfur compound primarily produced by
1241 phytoplankton. The intracellular ratio of DMSP to carbon biomass varies significantly among
1242 phytoplankton functional types, ranging up to four orders of magnitude (Stefels et al., 2007),
1243 highlighting the importance of phytoplankton diversity in DMS production. The production of
1244 DMSP and DMS will change as a result of not only warming but also acidification

1245 (Schwinger et al., 2017; Six et al., 2013). However, estimates on projected DMS changes
1246 using the current-generation climate models neither fully account for these environmental
1247 effects nor these models incorporate sufficient phytoplankton diversity (Bock et al., 2021).

1248 Using the output of the 35-compartment phytoplankton model projection (Cael et al., 2021;
1249 Henson et al., 2021), we illustrate potential regional-scale abrupt shifts in DMSP during the
1250 21st century. By multiplying the modelled phytoplankton biomass of the six functional types
1251 by their respective observed intracellular ratios, we derive the annual mean sea surface
1252 DMSP distribution averaged over the present period (2005-2024; Figure 6a) and the
1253 projected percentage changes by the end of the 21st century (2081-2100; Figure 6b). The
1254 DMSP time series from 1991 to 2100 at each grid point are fitted using both linear
1255 regression (Virtanen et al., 2020) and a step function through an offline change point
1256 detection method (Truong et al., 2020). The identification of abrupt changes is based on a
1257 comparison of the root mean square error (RMSE) of the step function to that of the linear
1258 fit, considering changes as abrupt when the ratio of the step-function RMSE to the linear-fit
1259 RMSE is less than 0.99.

1260 Projected DMSP changes are characterised by a high (close to 100%) increase in sub-polar
1261 regions (beyond 40°N/S) and a decrease in the tropics and sub-tropics (Figure 6b).
1262 Henson's et al, (2021) work analyses the association with projected changes in
1263 phytoplankton biomass and notice that in the areas above DMS and phytoplankton
1264 biomass patterns are similar. However, there are regions, such as the Bay of Bengal and
1265 the Iceland Basin, where DMSP changes are prominent despite subtle biomass and
1266 diversity changes (Figures 1a and 1b of Henson et al., 2021). Regression analysis indicates
1267 gradual DMSP increases in these regions (Figure 6b). Abrupt shifts are projected to occur
1268 in various regions without a clear pattern regarding potential drivers, such as phytoplankton
1269 biomass and community composition.

1270 In summary, our results suggest that the contribution of marine ecosystems to radiative
1271 forcing through DMS emission is likely to change gradually at the global scale (Figure 6c),
1272 while abrupt changes may occur at the regional scale during the 21st century (Figure 6b, d).
1273 These regional abrupt changes in DMS may be crucial for new particle formation in areas
1274 with low background cloud condensation nuclei, such as the Arctic (Sharma et al., 2012). It
1275 is crucial to note that our results are based on a basic parameterisation of intracellular
1276 DMSP-to-carbon ratios, intended to demonstrate the possibility of abrupt changes in DMSP
1277 in the coming decades. In reality, these ratios vary significantly within and among species,
1278 strongly depending on environmental conditions such as nutrient stress and acidification
1279 (Six et al., 2013). A more accurate projection requires a sophisticated parameterisation
1280 (McParland and Levine, 2019). Further advancements in both modelling and remote
1281 sensing of phytoplankton functional types are essential for accurate quantification of DMSP
1282 in the ocean and monitoring the tipping point for the regional phytoplankton-aerosol-cloud
1283 feedback.

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Figure 6: Abrupt shifts in dimethylsulfoniopropionate (DMSP) in the global ocean during the 21st century derived from the output of a 35-compartment phytoplankton model projection based on a high greenhouse gas emission scenario. (a) Global distribution of annual mean sea surface DMSP averaged over 2005-2024, (b) projected percentage change in annual mean sea surface DMSP averaged over 2081-2100 relative to the period 2005-2024, and time series of annual mean sea surface DMSP (c) averaged over 65°S-65°N and (d) at a location in the North Pacific subtropical gyre denoted by a purple circle in (b). DMSP is derived by multiplying the modelled carbon biomass of dinoflagellates by 22, coccolithophores by 11, diatoms by 0.86, and diazotrophs/prokaryotes/picokaryotes by 0.0015, which are the observed mean intracellular ratios for these phytoplankton functional types (Stefels et al., 2007; M. Galí and J. Stefels, personal communication, September 2023). In (b), hatches represent areas where the step-function outperforms the linear regression in fitting the projected time series over 1991-2100 at each grid point. In (c) and (d), orange and red lines represent the best fit based on linear regression and step function, respectively. Numbers in parentheses represent the root mean square error of each fit. See the main text for details.

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1302 3.1.2 EO needs and opportunities

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Detection and early warning of tipping points for these elements require further investigation into the various environmental factors influencing productivity and diversity, along with assessment through modeling. Long-term monitoring of phytoplankton productivity and diversity through remote sensing has proven effective in understanding global-scale patterns (Groom et al., 2019) and their responses to gradual climate changes (Cael et al., 2023). Continuous investment in this monitoring effort is essential to advance knowledge in the coming decades. Two ongoing satellite missions, the Global Change Observation Mission – Climate "SHIKISAI" (GCOM-C; https://global.jaxa.jp/projects/sat/gcom_c/) and the Plankton, Aerosol, Cloud, and ocean Ecosystem (PACE; <https://pace.gsfc.nasa.gov/>), offer prospects over the next decade, and additional missions are crucial for the future. Simultaneously, it is important to enhance the calibration of multiple missions to detect decadal changes.

1315 Further improvements are needed in algorithms for identifying multiple phytoplankton
1316 groups, and these enhancements should occur concurrently with the parallel development
1317 of models. For instance, considering the significance of phytoplankton species composition
1318 in shaping the DMSP distribution, a top priority should be to increase the number of
1319 phytoplankton functional types in Earth System Models (ESMs), ideally to six as
1320 recommended by Stefels et al. (2007). Such an implementation would enable the
1321 assessment of the suitability of existing models with simpler complexity for projection
1322 studies (Bock et al. 2021) and open up new opportunities for further exploration.

1323 **3.2 Zooplankton**

1324 **3.2.1 Nature of tipping point**

1325 Marine zooplankton can be considered a tipping element in marine ecosystems due to their
1326 central role in maintaining the balance and functionality of oceanic food webs and
1327 biogeochemical cycles: marine zooplankton are in fact fundamental to ocean ecosystems
1328 and global biogeochemical cycles, serving as a critical link between primary producers, like
1329 phytoplankton, and higher trophic levels, including fish, seabirds and marine mammals.
1330 Through their feeding activities, zooplankton help regulate phytoplankton populations, thus
1331 influencing primary production and the overall energy flow within marine food webs.
1332 Additionally, zooplankton play a key role in the "biological pump," a process that contributes
1333 to carbon sequestration. By consuming phytoplankton and converting this organic matter
1334 into fecal pellets, which sink to the ocean floor, zooplankton facilitate the transport of carbon
1335 from the surface to the deep ocean, effectively removing it from the atmosphere and
1336 helping mitigate climate change (Steinberg & Landry, 2017; Turner, 2015). Tipping points
1337 and abrupt shifts in marine zooplankton populations can therefore be extremely important
1338 because they can trigger significant and potentially irreversible changes in marine
1339 ecosystems and global biogeochemical cycles.

1340 Abrupt community shifts (ACSs) in zooplankton have been documented in various marine
1341 ecosystems, providing valuable insights into ecological dynamics. Notable instances
1342 include occurrences in the North Pacific during 1976/1977 and 1989, as extensively studied
1343 by Ebbesmeyer et al. (1991), Francis and Hare (1994), Hare and Mantua (2000), Polovina
1344 (2005), and Field et al. (2006). Specifically, the north-east Pacific witnessed ACSs in
1345 1976/1977 (McGowan et al. 2003, Miller et al. 2004) and 1998/1999 (Peterson and Schwing
1346 2003, Lavaniegos and Ohman 2007), while the north-west Pacific experienced shifts in
1347 1976/1977, 1988/1989, and 1998 (Chiba et al. 2006, Kasai and Ono 2007, Sakurai 2007).
1348 The Humboldt Current in the southern Pacific also observed ACSs in 1968/1970 and
1349 1984/1986 (Alheit and Niquen 2004, Alheit 2009). In the north-west Atlantic, a notable event
1350 occurred in 1989/1990, documented by Frank et al. (2005), Pershing et al. (2005), Greene
1351 and Pershing (2007), Greene et al. (2012), and Greene et al. (2013).

1352 Additionally, abrupt community shifts have been identified in European seas during the late
1353 1980s, affecting the North Sea (Reid et al. 2001, Weijerman et al. 2005); the Baltic Sea
1354 (Alheit et al. 2005, Moellmann et al. 2009), and the north-west European shelf seas
1355 (1987/1990) (Beaugrand 2004, Heath and Beare 2008; the Black Sea (Daskalov et al.
1356 2007, Oguz 2007) and the western and eastern (Adriatic) Mediterranean Sea (Molinero et
1357 al. 2008, Conversi et al. 2010). This synchronicity of these shifts was investigated by
1358 Conversi et al, 2010 and Beaugrand et al 2015, among others.

1359 In the late 1990s, ACSs were observed in the north-east Atlantic and adjacent seas, the
1360 Black Sea, and San Francisco Bay (Oguz et al. 2003, Cloern et al. 2010, Luczak et al.
1361 2011, Beaugrand et al. 2013). These shifts coincided with a global temperature shift around
1362 the same time (Reid and Beaugrand 2012). The ACS in the late 1970s originated from
1363 changes in large-scale boreal winter circulation patterns over the North Pacific in the mid-

1364 1970s, altering the environmental regime of these oceanic regions (Miller et al. 1994,
1365 Tsonis et al. 2007).

1366 Explanations for ACSs in zooplankton often reference the theory of alternative stable states
1367 (Holling 1973, Scheffer and Carpenter 2003, Scheffer 2009). While some ecosystem shifts
1368 may result from multiple attractors, establishing their existence remains challenging
1369 (Seekell et al. 2013). Processes and alternative stable states leading to ACSs have been
1370 recognized in lakes and some marine ecosystems (Nystrom et al. 2000, Scheffer and van
1371 Nes 2004, Scheffer 2009). Utilizing the METAL theory (MacroEcological Theory on the
1372 Arrangement of Life, Beaugrand and Kirby 2018, Beaugrand 2023), Beaugrand (2015)
1373 demonstrated that many ACSs in zooplankton could arise from the nonlinear interaction
1374 between the ecological niche of individual species and environmental changes without
1375 necessarily invoking the existence of a tipping point. Subsequently, Beaugrand et al. (2019)
1376 developed a global numerical model based on METAL to understand and predict long-term
1377 biological changes in oceans, including ACSs, effectively reconstructing well-observed
1378 shifts in the pelagic ocean (Figure 7).

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Figure 7. Comparison of predicted (blue) and observed (red) biological shifts. Predictions were made using a model based on the MacroEcological Theory on the Arrangement of Life (METAL). Observations were synthesised using a principal component analysis combining 14 oceanic regions (Atlantic, Southern and Pacific oceans and their adjacent seas). Green curves show results using random models. The y-axis represents arbitrary standardised indicators of the biological state of the ecosystems. Negative and positive states have contrasting effects on the ecosystems.

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1381 The framework was subsequently applied globally for the period 1960-2015 to pinpoint
1382 areas where major biological shifts are likely. The analyses revealed that significant
1383 biological shifts may occur annually but are confined to a limited part of the ocean,
1384 averaging approximately 2.8% of the total oceanic area, translating to an average area of
1385 around 10 million km² per year. Certain periods, such as 2005-2009, exhibited
1386 geographically restricted shifts, while others, like 2010-2014, demonstrated more extensive

1387 ones (see Figure 8). The spatial extent of the biological shifts in 2010-2014 was particularly
1388 noteworthy and stemmed from the simultaneous occurrence of four phenomena: (i) a
1389 pronounced El Niño event (2015-2016)¹⁹, (ii) the Pacific warm blob (an anomaly featuring
1390 positive temperatures in the north-eastern part of the North Pacific), (iii) the Atlantic cold
1391 blob (a cold temperature anomaly in the central part of the North Atlantic), and (iv) strong
1392 positive temperature anomalies in the Arctic Ocean (Beaugrand et al. 2019).
1393

Figure 8. Results from the global METAL model for time periods 2005-2009 (top) and 2010-2014 (bottom). The red colours denote substantial biological shifts and the yellow colours indicate minor changes. No colour denotes an absence of biological shifts.

1394 **3.2.2 EO needs and opportunities**

1395 Given the crucial role that marine zooplankton plays in ocean ecosystems and global
1396 biogeochemical cycles, there is a growing need to monitor zooplankton populations on

¹⁹ Note that the calculation of a shift for a given year was based on a three-year period. Therefore, the time periods shown here embrace 1 year before and after in the calculation; 2005-2009 and 2010-2014 include 2004-2010 and 2009-2015.

Opportunities for Earth Observation to inform risk management for ocean tipping points

1397 large spatial and temporal scales. Earth Observation (EO) technologies offer potential
1398 solutions, though studying zooplankton from space presents unique challenges.

1399 Direct observation of individual zooplankton from space is not feasible due to their small
1400 size. However, proxy measurements and indirect methods, such as using ocean colour
1401 data, show promise. For instance, zooplankton abundance can be inferred from satellite-
1402 derived chlorophyll concentrations, their primary food source. Strömberg et al. (2009;
1403 doi:10.1016/j.jmarsys.2009.02.004) demonstrated a relationship between chlorophyll-a
1404 concentrations and global zooplankton patterns. However, Friedland et al. (2018;
1405 https://doi.org/10.1111/geb.12717) showed that these relationships vary significantly across
1406 regions and seasons, complicating the use of satellite data for accurate zooplankton
1407 estimates.

1408 Isolating the optical signature of zooplankton from other particulate matter in the water
1409 remains a significant challenge. Developing algorithms to separate the zooplankton
1410 contribution to ocean colour signals is crucial for improving the accuracy of zooplankton
1411 studies using EO data. Frouin et al. (2019; https://doi.org/10.3389/feart.2019.00145)
1412 reviewed advances in atmospheric correction for ocean colour remote sensing,
1413 underscoring its importance for the accurate estimation of bio-optical properties related to
1414 plankton. Persistent cloud cover in certain regions further complicates this issue,
1415 necessitating methods to work with limited or intermittent data. Moreover, managing both
1416 random and systematic errors is crucial to ensure the accuracy and reliability of the data.

1417 Most zooplankton inhabit subsurface layers not directly observable from satellites, requiring
1418 innovative methods to infer subsurface conditions from surface observations. Techniques
1419 developed by Sauzède et al. (2015; https://doi.org/10.5194/essd-7-261-2015) for estimating
1420 vertical chlorophyll profiles from satellite data could potentially be adapted for zooplankton
1421 studies. Additionally, high-frequency satellite observations, such as those from the
1422 Geostationary Ocean Color Imager (GOCI), can capture short-term variability in plankton
1423 communities (Li et al., 2022; https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2022.115311). Behrenfeld et
1424 al. (2019; https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-019-1796-9) utilized satellite lidar to observe diel
1425 vertical migration of zooplankton, though this technology is not yet widely available.

1426 Distinguishing between different zooplankton species or functional groups from space is
1427 extremely challenging. Alvain et al. (2008; https://doi.org/10.1029/2007GB003154) created
1428 a method to identify phytoplankton functional types from ocean colour data, which could
1429 serve as a model for similar approaches in zooplankton research.

1430 Another challenge is the validation of zooplankton-related products derived from satellite
1431 data. Extensive in-situ sampling is necessary (Druon et al., 2019;
1432 https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-019-41212-2). However, combining satellite data with in-situ
1433 measurements involves substantial technical and methodological challenges due to
1434 differences in scale, coverage, and measurement techniques.

1435 The examination of abrupt shifts and their attribution to environmental drivers, detailed in
1436 Section 3.2.1, highlights the critical significance of global-scale coverage encompassing
1437 both physical parameters like sea surface temperature (SST) and biological variables such
1438 as colour, facilitated by EO. Coordinated international efforts are essential for advancing
1439 high-resolution remote sensing and data integration capabilities to handle the large volumes
1440 of high-resolution data required to accurately represent the Earth's surface. Addressing
1441 inter-sensor biases is also critical for long-term monitoring and avoiding false trends
1442 (Balsamo et al., 2019; https://doi.org/10.3390/rs11080941; Sathyendranath et al., 2023;
1443 https://doi.org/10.1007/s10712-023-09805-9).

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1446 **3.3 Higher trophic levels and fisheries**

1447 **3.3.1 Nature of tipping point**

1448 Pelagic ecosystems, particularly over continental shelves, do not operate in isolation, and the
1449 nonlinear interaction between plankton species and environmental changes can have
1450 cascading effects throughout the entire trophic food web. Numerous instances in the scientific
1451 literature (Lindley et al. 2010, Luczak et al. 2011, Luczak et al. 2012) exemplify this
1452 phenomenon. For instance, a study revealed a surge in the population of balearic shearwater
1453 (*Puffinus mauretanicus*) during the mid-1990s in the north-east Atlantic (17°W-4°E and 48°N-
1454 60°N). Concurrently, significant changes in a zooplankton composition index from the
1455 Continuous Plankton Recorder (CPR) survey were noted, along with a stepwise increase in
1456 the abundance of sardine and anchovy, the primary diet of the seabird (Luczak et al. 2011).

1457 In regions over continental shelves, pelagic and benthic ecosystems are intricately linked,
1458 and alterations in pelagic ecosystems have pronounced impacts on benthic ecosystems
1459 (Lindley et al. 2010, Luczak et al. 2012). Profound transformations in the North Sea
1460 ecosystems, occurring at the end of the 1980s and from the middle to the end of the 1990s,
1461 were observed (Reid et al. 2001, Beaugrand et al. 2014). The abrupt rise in temperature
1462 significantly disrupted the trophodynamics of pelagic ecosystems, subsequently affecting
1463 benthic communities (Lindley et al. 2010). In the late 1990s, an increase in swimming crabs
1464 further influenced the reproductive success of lesser black-backed gull (*Larus fuscus*
1465 *graelii*), establishing a connection between marine ecosystem shifts and terrestrial ecology
1466 (Luczak et al. 2012).

1467 Alterations in the composition of North Sea zooplankton also had a considerable impact on
1468 commercially exploited fish, such as Atlantic cod (*Gadus morhua*). Post the late 1980s,
1469 changes in small planktonic crustaceans, crucial as the primary food for larval cod, occurred
1470 with a reduction in size, abundance, and biomass (Beaugrand et al. 2003). The timing of the
1471 main peak in copepod abundance shifted later in the year, coinciding with the period when
1472 fish larvae had matured and were no longer reliant on these small prey organisms. Combined
1473 with overfishing, these abrupt shifts adversely affected larval cod recruitment.

1474 A novel model based on the METAL theory has demonstrated how overfishing and
1475 environmental changes can interact to impact cod recruitment and biomass in the North Sea
1476 (Beaugrand et al. 2022). The identification of a tipping point and the suggestion of hysteresis
1477 under certain conditions emphasize the complex dynamics. Overexploitation can swiftly
1478 deplete fish stocks (Christensen et al. 2003, Pauly et al. 2003). Beaugrand et al. (2022)
1479 illustrated that, in favourable environmental conditions and with a hypothetical moratorium,
1480 recovery may occur, but the time required is lengthier than the duration of fishing-induced
1481 depletion. The recovery duration is influenced by the interaction between the low stock level
1482 and the initially slow exponential population growth phase, dependent on the stock's growth
1483 coefficient. However, when environmental conditions become unfavourable, recovery may
1484 become exceedingly challenging, spanning decades or even be impossible if adverse
1485 conditions persist, indicating irreversibility.

1486 This example also elucidates why, despite a fishing moratorium near Newfoundland,
1487 recovery, albeit partial, took more than two decades (DFO 2018). Notably, recovery proves
1488 problematic for numerous other fish stocks (e.g., haddock, flatfish, Hutchings 2000). Hence,
1489 preventing collapse emerges as a more attainable goal than attempting to reverse it.
1490 Rebuilding a stock remains achievable only if environmental conditions remain conducive
1491 (Möllmann et al. 2021).

1492 **3.3.2 EO needs and opportunities**

1493 In this section, we review the significant challenges and promising opportunities associated
1494 with using Earth Observation (EO) to study higher trophic levels and fisheries.

1495 Challenges:

- 1496 1. Indirect Observations: One major obstacle is the inability to directly observe higher
1497 trophic species from space, which necessitates the use of proxy measurements and
1498 habitat modeling. This indirect approach is complicated by the complex, non-linear
1499 relationships between environmental conditions and higher trophic levels, as well as
1500 time lags between observable environmental changes and their effects on species.
1501 These factors make it difficult to establish clear cause-and-effect relationships and
1502 accurately interpret EO data (Grémillet and Boulinier, 2009;
1503 <https://doi.org/10.3354/meps08212>). The temporal mismatch between
1504 environmental changes and biological responses can obscure true relationships
1505 between oceanographic conditions and species distributions or abundances (Visser
1506 and Both, 2005; <https://doi.org/10.1098/rspb.2005.3356>). This issue is particularly
1507 pronounced for long-lived species, where environmental effects may only become
1508 apparent after significant delays (Durant et al., 2007; doi:10.3354/cr033271).
1509 Additionally, the limited historical record of EO data (Swingedouw et al., 2020;
1510 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10712-020-09604-6>) and methodological consistency
1511 problems when reconstructing long time series from different sensors
1512 (Sathyendranath et al., 2023; <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10712-023-09805-9>) further
1513 complicate the analysis.
- 1514 2. Data integration Issues: Similar to the other biological components, Integrating EO
1515 data with in-situ observations, catch data, and ecosystem models is crucial for a
1516 comprehensive understanding of marine ecosystems but faces several challenges.
1517 Differences in data resolution, scale, and format can hinder this integration (Rose et
1518 al., 2015; <https://doi.org/10.1111/cobi.12397>). The processes affecting fisheries and
1519 higher trophic levels often occur at scales that do not align with the resolution of
1520 available EO data, potentially missing fine-scale movements and leading to
1521 challenges in representing ecosystem dynamics (Rose et al., 2015;
1522 <https://doi.org/10.1111/cobi.12397>; Kavanaugh et al., 2016;
1523 <https://doi.org/10.1093/icesjms/fsw086>).

1524 Opportunities:

- 1525 1. Monitoring Fishing Activities: EO has proven valuable in monitoring fishing activities.
1526 Kroodsma et al. (2018; doi:10.1126/science.aao5646) utilised AIS data and satellite
1527 imagery to create a global map of fishing effort, providing insights into the spatial
1528 and temporal patterns of fishing activities. This information is essential for enforcing
1529 fishing regulations and designing effective marine protected areas.
- 1530 2. Habitat Modeling: Significant progress has been made in using satellite-derived
1531 oceanographic data to model and map potential habitats for species such as the
1532 blue shark (Druon et al., 2022; <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2022.828412>). Muller-
1533 Karger et al. (2018; doi:10.3389/fmars.2018.00211) proposed a framework for
1534 integrating satellite observations with in-situ data and models to support ecosystem-
1535 based management of fisheries and marine resources. However, these approaches
1536 still require refinement.
- 1537 3. Data Integration Advances: A strategic combination of remote sensing, in situ
1538 observations, and appropriate modelling is essential (Stuart et al. 2011). EO
1539 technology addresses critical gaps, providing an opportunity for all countries and
1540 individuals, even those without the capacity to collect essential data, to contribute to

1541 local solutions for global challenges (e.g., Almar et al. 2022). Recent advances in
1542 data assimilation techniques have shown promise in bridging the gap between
1543 satellite observations and ecosystem models (de Souza et al., 2016;
1544 <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0163760>; Schwartz-Belkin & Portman, 2023;
1545 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ocecoaman.2022.106280>). By implementing models trained
1546 on a combination of EO and in situ data, Hazen et al. (2018) introduce an innovative
1547 multispecies and dynamic approach that utilises daily satellite data to monitor ocean
1548 features, aligning the scales of management, species movement, and fisheries.

1549 4. Policy advances: Policy makers must understand the significance of satellite EO
1550 data in evidence-based decision-making. For example, NASA's Applied Sciences
1551 Programme within the Earth Science Division offers free training on the practical
1552 application of satellite data, covering objectives such as fisheries management
1553 (Andries et al. 2022). Global Fishing Watch builds geospatial datasets and hosts an
1554 online mapping platform that allows anyone with internet access to monitor various
1555 types of ocean-going vessels, sharing data and map products with scientists and
1556 practitioners, notwithstanding challenges discussed in Drakopoulos et al. (2022).

1557 Future efforts should focus on improving our ability to detect and predict tipping points in
1558 marine ecosystems. This can be achieved through higher-resolution satellite data, improved
1559 algorithms for detecting subtle changes in ecosystem indicators, and better methods for
1560 integrating multiple data sources to identify early warning signs of ecological shifts.

1561 Integrating remote sensing EO technology with environmental decision-making enhances the
1562 efficiency and sustainability of solutions. Therefore, the broader scientific community must
1563 consistently support programs that enable the application of satellite EO data for global
1564 societal benefit and the stewardship of our planet (Kansakar & Hossain, 2016).

1565

1566 **3.4 Marine biodiversity and biomass**

1567 **3.4.1 Nature of tipping point**

1568 While human activities, such as fishing, pollution, and species invasion, exert a significant
1569 impact on pelagic marine biodiversity, global climate change also plays a substantial role.
1570 However, assessing the extent of this stressor and the presence of tipping points remains
1571 challenging due to data and theoretical approach limitations.

1572 A theoretical framework based on METAL estimated the vulnerability of global ocean
1573 biodiversity to climate change (Beaugrand et al. 2015). This framework suggested that
1574 climate change could swiftly reorganise marine biodiversity across extensive oceanic
1575 regions. Observations have since confirmed an increase in marine biodiversity in
1576 extratropical regions (Hiddink and Hofstedeter 2008, Gordó-Vilaseca et al. 2023), aligning
1577 with the model's predictions. Rapid and substantial changes in marine biodiversity occurred
1578 in the north-east Atlantic and its adjacent seas in the late 1980s, influencing the entire
1579 trophodynamics of the North Sea across phytoplankton, fish, pelagic and benthic realms,
1580 and extending to terrestrial ecosystems (Beaugrand 2009). Although no clear tipping point
1581 has been identified, these changes are believed to result from the nonlinear interaction
1582 between species' ecological niches and shifts in the environmental regime (Beaugrand and
1583 Kirby 2018).

1584 Comparisons of biodiversity changes expected by the end of this century with those
1585 observed between the last glacial maximum (LGM; about 20,000 years ago) and today, or
1586 between the mid-Pliocene (2.3 million years ago) and today, offer insights. The study
1587 highlights that the intensity of biodiversity reorganization depends on the magnitude of
1588 warming (Beaugrand et al. 2015). Under scenarios of small global warming (RCP2.6),
1589 biological changes would be relatively benign, reflecting a modest percentage of historical

1590 changes. However, for moderate warming (RCP4.5), changes in marine biodiversity are
1591 considerably more extensive and robust than those observed over the past 50 years. In the
1592 case of severe global warming (RCP6.0 and 8.5), a substantial portion of the global ocean
1593 experiences a change in marine biodiversity equivalent to or exceeding that observed
1594 between the LGM/mid-Pliocene and today. This underscores the significant impact of
1595 climate warming on marine biodiversity. Any reorganization of marine biodiversity is bound
1596 to influence species interactions and, consequently, ecosystem functioning, provisioning,
1597 and regulating services (Cheung et al. 2009), emphasizing the importance of understanding
1598 the effects of climate change on biodiversity.

1599 **3.4.2 EO needs and opportunities**

1600 Earth Observation (EO) is crucial for species distribution mapping, particularly through
1601 habitat mapping. Satellites use spectral bands to identify marine habitats like coral reefs,
1602 seagrass beds, and kelp forests, with changes in these habitats indicating shifts in
1603 dependent species. For example, Landsat satellites have been instrumental in mapping
1604 coral reefs globally. Li et al. (2020; <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00338-020-02005-6>) used
1605 Landsat to create a global coral reef map, essential for understanding coral-dependent
1606 species distributions and detecting ecosystem tipping points. EO data combined with
1607 species distribution models helps predict suitable habitats and guide conservation efforts,
1608 as demonstrated by Yati et al. (2024; <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marenvres.2024.106540>),
1609 who used this approach to propose marine protected areas. Monitoring changes in
1610 predicted habitats over time allows detection of species distribution shifts, potentially
1611 indicating broader ecosystem changes.

1612 EO also facilitates direct observation of larger marine species or large multi-individual
1613 aggregations. High-resolution satellite imagery, such as WorldView-3, has been used to
1614 detect and count whales, as shown by Cubaynes et al. (2019;
1615 <https://doi.org/10.1111/mms.12544>). Similarly, satellites equipped with ocean color sensors,
1616 such as MODIS, can map harmful algal blooms, which impact marine ecosystems, as
1617 demonstrated in studies by Zhao et al. (2020;
1618 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envadv.2020.100008>) and others.

1619 Satellite imagery is also useful in mapping seabird colonies, such as Lynch et al.'s (2012;
1620 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00300-011-1138-3>) survey of Adélie penguins in Antarctica.

1621 Evaluating and monitoring future biodiversity requires robust models, similar to those used
1622 in generating Figure 9. These models should be calibrated and evaluated based on recent
1623 biodiversity changes, using environmental parameters often derived from remote sensing.
1624 Additionally, empirical and data-driven early warning approaches, as demonstrated by
1625 studies like Dakos et al. (2010) and Verbesselt et al. (2016), present promising avenues.
1626 These approaches can be directly fuelled by Earth Observation (EO) data or utilize the
1627 outputs of ecosystem models.

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1630 **Figure 9.** Past and future quantitative (left-hand maps) and qualitative (right-hand maps) change in
 1631 marine biodiversity. Maps on top four rows (a-d and g-j) show the difference between projected
 1632 future (2081-2100) and present (2006-13) under the four emissions scenarios. Maps on bottom two
 1633 rows show difference between the last glacial maximum (LGM, maps e and k) and 1960-69, and the
 1634 Mid-Pliocene (maps f and l) and 2006-13. Regions of largest percentage change shown as oranges
 1635 and reds, and smaller changes as blues and greens. From Beaugrand and colleagues (Beaugrand et
 1636 al. 2015).

1637

1638

1639 Future EO needs and opportunities include:

- 1640 • Hyperspectral sensors for improved habitat discrimination
- 1641 • Higher temporal resolution data from geostationary satellites
- 1642 • Improved atmospheric correction algorithms for coastal waters
- 1643 • LiDAR technology for detailed coastal topography and bathymetry
- 1644 • Advanced SAR systems for all-weather monitoring of marine environments

1645 The development of data fusion techniques and integrated satellite platforms, which
1646 combine data from optical, radar, and thermal sensors, holds significant promise,
1647 e.g., Moroni et al. (2016; <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2015.07.045>). This multi-sensor
1648 approach, coupled with advanced algorithms and AI, as shown by Guirado et al. (2019;
1649 <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-019-50795-9>) for detecting whales, is revolutionising
1650 ecological research.

1651 Advancements in EO technology, like higher resolution sensors optimised for coastal and
1652 inland waters, offer new opportunities for monitoring complex environments. Kutser et al.
1653 (2016; <https://doi.org/10.1080/01431161.2016.1186852>) reviewed these methods,
1654 emphasising their importance for fine-scale ecological monitoring. Developing new
1655 biodiversity metrics based on EO data is crucial for conservation, as discussed by Petteorelli
1656 et al. (2016; <https://doi.org/10.1002/rse2.15>), while long-term data consistency, as stressed
1657 by Mélin et al. (2017; <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2017.03.039>), is essential for tracking
1658 ecological changes.

1659 Combining EO with in-situ data enhances the accuracy of biodiversity assessments. Muller-
1660 Karger et al. (2018; <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2018.00211>) proposed a framework for
1661 such integration, which is vital for a holistic understanding of ecosystems. Advances in
1662 satellite-derived bathymetry and seafloor classification, as reviewed by Hedley et al. (2016;
1663 <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs8020118>), hold promise for better mapping of underwater habitats.
1664 Integrating satellite observations with emerging techniques like environmental DNA (eDNA)
1665 sampling, or data from biogeochemical-Argo floats could provide a more comprehensive
1666 picture of marine biodiversity, as explored by Yamasaki et al. (2017;
1667 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cosust.2018.03.005>) and Sauzède et al. (2016;
1668 <https://doi.org/10.1002/2015JC011408>).

1669 Cloud-based platforms and standardised data products are key for timely biodiversity
1670 assessments. Duffy et al. (2019; <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2019.00317>) emphasised the
1671 importance of near-real-time EO data for conservation.

1672 Looking ahead, satellite-based acoustic sensors could monitor underwater noise levels,
1673 potentially affecting marine life. While still in its early stages, this innovative approach,
1674 discussed by Sun et al. (2021; <https://doi.org/10.3390/s21237849>), represents the kind of
1675 innovative thinking needed to fully leverage EO for marine biodiversity monitoring. These
1676 advancements will significantly enhance our ability to monitor and understand marine
1677 ecosystems using Earth Observation technologies.

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1679 **4. Synthesis and prospects**

1680
1681 Specific needs for Earth Observation (EO) depend strongly on the detail of the Tipping
1682 Element under consideration, and the reader is referred to the individual TE discussions in

1683 Sections 2 and 3 of this paper. However, some common themes emerge. These themes
1684 are not all unique to ocean tipping points, but the nature of the ocean and of abrupt
1685 changes places particular emphasis on some of them. References are given beside each
1686 point below to relevant TE-specific discussion in earlier sections:

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- The value of long-term, uninterrupted and homogeneous timeseries is clear in several areas, and is particularly important when studying abrupt changes that span decadal timescales (e.g. AMOC §2.2.2, ecosystem dynamics, especially involving long-lived species, §3.2.2, 3.3.2). Issues of continuity and cross-calibration should therefore be high on the agenda of future mission planning, as well as resolving apparent differences between alternative instruments or products (e.g. polar SSS, §2.2.2)
- An important role for EO emerges in monitoring and early detection of changes in critical fine scale processes (e.g. transports through Arctic gateways §2.3.2, 2.4.2, submesoscale dynamics §2.5.2, patchy and moving planktonic systems §3.1.2, 3.2.2). In many cases the value of EO for this purpose can only be realised through combination with *in situ*, and *model* data (especially for processes involving the sub-surface ocean, which is not directly accessible to EO). Machine Learning, perhaps trained on high resolution process-resolving models, provides particular new opportunities to integrate multiple datasets, augmenting the spatial and temporal resolution, and vertical coverage, of EO.
- Another important role for EO is in providing ‘truth’ data to assess and develop parametrisations of fine scale processes for use in coarser models (e.g. air-sea-ice interactions §2.2.2, 2.3.2). Many models used for large scale climate assessments lack resolution in key areas (e.g. in space, time or ecosystem complexity).
- In other cases, state-of-the-art models (especially regional or subsystem-specific models) are ahead of current EO capabilities in resolution or complexity (e.g. multi-species ecosystem models, §3.3, 3.4). This creates a demand for higher resolution or accuracy than is possible with current EO systems. As well as driving future technological improvements, the existence of complex models provides opportunities to develop improved algorithms to maximise the information extracted from existing instruments, including EO-derived proxies for variables that cannot be observed directly. Again, Machine Learning is opening up new possibilities in this area.
- Combination or joint analysis of several data types is challenging, and in some cases methods of consistently assimilating multiple data types into (inevitably biased) models are a limiting factor in obtaining full value from existing EO datasets (e.g. for decadal prediction systems, §2.2.2). Developments in modelling and multivariate data assimilation must therefore proceed in tandem with future observational developments if the full potential of EO is to be realised.
- While data assimilating models, incorporating multiple data streams, offer a long term path to monitoring and early warning, alternative methods of analysis based directly on EO data can provide valuable insights. For example, empirical methods for identifying approaching tipping through linking the changing properties of timeseries to simple conceptual models of tipping dynamics (e.g. critical slowing down §2.1, or space-for-time, §2.2), are well suited to the high spatial or temporal resolution of many EO datasets. The advent of high-resolution models and machine

1735 learning techniques opens up many new possibilities for training and evaluating
1736 such methods.

1737

1738 ● It will never be possible to observe everything we would like to in sufficient detail. So
1739 inevitably, indirect or proxy relationships will need to be used between observed
1740 variables and the actual system variable of interest (e.g. various AMOC proxies
1741 §2.1.2, key elements of the oxygen cycle §2.6.2, indicators of ecosystem structure
1742 §3.2.2, 3.3.2). When developing empirical early warning indicators and proxies, it
1743 will be important to build confidence through model studies that such methods can
1744 detect the changes that may occur in future, as well as what has happened in the
1745 past (e.g. for AMOC §2.1.1). For long timescale processes palaeoclimatic
1746 data/model studies may be an important source of calibration (e.g. biogeochemical
1747 processes §2.6). It will also be important to establish that relationships developed
1748 for one region are also applicable to other regions (e.g. for planktonic ecosystems
1749 §3.2.2) Specific attention should be paid to the combination of different
1750 observables, both EO and *in situ*, to increase the robustness of warning signals
1751 (e.g., a combination of temperature and salinity, both surface and subsurface and
1752 from different locations, to derive an early warning indicator for AMOC or SPG,
1753 §2.1.2, 2.2.2).

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1755 ● The multivariate approaches outlined above imply an increasing need for
1756 improvements in data standardisation and accessibility, despite the challenges of
1757 differing space-time scales, timeliness, quality assurance and error characteristics
1758 (see e.g. discussion in §3.3.2). This presents a particular challenge to the
1759 international scientific community, as solutions developed for a particular problem
1760 may not be useful in the context of another.

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1763 As the focus of climate science moves from establishing the challenges of climate change,
1764 to supporting societal responses to those challenges, so the demand for detail in monitoring
1765 changes in the climate system increases. The likelihood of crossing climate tipping points is
1766 expected to increase as the climate warms (IPCC 2021), and there is an urgent need for a
1767 joined-up approach, integrating EO and *in situ* observations with climate modelling,
1768 downstream impacts assessment and societal decision-making and policy (Wood et al.
1769 2023). Earth Observation has a key role to play in avoiding the worst risks of climate
1770 tipping, and in building resilience to those risks that cannot be avoided.

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